

D3.1

Analysis of the Transport network and Land use dynamics

Revision v0.2

Work package	WP3
Task	T3.1
Due date	28-02-2026
Submission date	27-02-2026
Deliverable lead	AUTh
Version	V0.2
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Abstract

Deliverable D3.1 "Analysis of the Transport network and Land use dynamics" is the key output of Task T3.1 within Work Package 3 (WP3) of the AntifragiCity project. This task aims to analyze the connection between land use and transport networks as a fundamental concept for designing safe, efficient, sustainable, and resilient transport systems. Land use and transport infrastructure are closely interlinked, underpinned theoretically in the so-called transport land-use feedback cycle. Still, nowadays, cities are challenged to meet new goals based on Climate Neutral and Smart Cities Mission, the Urban Sustainability Goals and the Road Safety Goals while increasing resilience and capabilities to deal with future uncertainties. Based on the findings of Task T2.1 and T2.5 and the KPIs of Task 2.7, the Deliverable 3.1 addresses three core objectives aligned with Task T3.1:

To analyze the transport network and land use dynamics in terms of current and future vulnerabilities, stressors and needs.

To understand the challenges and opportunities for evolving the transport land-use cycle analyzing the policy, legislative and strategic frameworks.

To develop a holistic urban mobility dynamics model that aligns with future challenges and promotes a human-driven perspective that supports future mobility needs and emergencies in line with land use and planning while minimizing the environmental impact.

Keywords

Transport network, land use dynamics, transport-land use feedback cycle, resilience, antifragility

Version	Date	Description of change	Contributor(s)
V0.1	30-01-2026	1st version of deliverable	Fotini Kehagia, Maria Tsami
V0.2	26-02-2026	2 nd version of deliverable	Fotini Kehagia, Anastasia Tzioutziou

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Funded by the European Union (grant agreement No 101203052).

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R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

AHEPA	AHEPA University Hospital in Thessaloniki
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AOI	Areas Of Interest
LUTI	Land-use/transport interaction
MaaS	Mobility as a Service
MLP	Multi-Level Perspective
O-D	Origin-Destination
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
TAZ	Traffic Analysis Zones
TOD	Transit-Oriented Development
WP	Work Package

1 Executive summary

This Deliverable D3.1 "*Analysis of the Transport network and Land use dynamics*" presents one of the outcomes from Work Package 3 (WP3) of the AntifragiCity project.

In the Deliverable, the connection between land use and transport networks as a fundamental concept for designing safe, efficient, sustainable, and resilient transport systems is analysed. For more than six decades, urban researchers have sought to formalize this relationship using mathematical, statistical, and logical methods, and to produce models capable of predicting changes to transportation and land use systems as the result of policy measures. The models have evolved from relatively simple, aggregate allocation schemes coupled to four-stage transport models to sophisticated microsimulation and agent-based platforms. The Land-use/transport interaction (LUTI) models as they provide formal representations of the bidirectional feedback between transport and land use, they have become key tools in strategic urban and transport planning, especially for ex-ante assessment of major infrastructure, pricing, and regulatory interventions.

Considering the new challenges and opportunities, which have emerged from the Strategic and Policy Framework of EU, the different Land-use/transport interaction (LUTI) models have to be more dynamic incorporating new dimensions for equilibrium.

Traditional approaches to urban mobility management prioritise efficiency and stability but they struggle to cope with the unpredictable and compounding nature of contemporary crises. Urban transportation systems are exposed to different types of disturbances or unexpected disruptive events or disasters. Mobility serves as the primary adaptive mechanism through which urban systems respond to and learn from disruptions.

The proposed holistic conceptual framework model aims to address urban mobility dynamics, integrating transport–land use interactions, resilience-oriented planning, human-centric design principles under conditions of uncertainty and external stressors. These interactions are not static, but they evolve over time and across spatial scales. The proposed framework extends beyond the broadly applied conceptualizations of resilience towards the approach of antifragility, enabling systems to learn and improve through disruption. Translating the conceptual approach of antifragility into transport–land-use planning means designing governance, standards, and investment rules so that disruptions systematically generate improvements rather than repeated reconstruction of the same vulnerabilities.

2 Introduction

2.1 Scope & Objectives

Modern urban areas, with their current layout and functioning, are hubs for a significant number of activities, creating the need for increased transport demand in order to meet the daily needs of citizens. Urban planning to date has been based on the development of car use, which has created numerous opportunities in terms of mobility, the economy, and social relations. The continuous increase in the movement of people and goods and the simultaneous increase in car use have caused significant problems in urban areas that affect citizens' quality of life, the environment, the economy, and transportation.

In recent years, transport system planning policy has changed radically. The conventional approach to transport planning, where the main priorities were to minimize travel time and increase mobility, has been replaced by the principles of sustainable urban mobility, with the primary objectives of increasing accessibility and promoting the balanced development of all modes of transport (Banister, 2008) (7). David Banister proposed four courses of action to achieve this goal: (1) reducing the need for travel-substitution, (2) implementing transport policy measures to facilitate modal shift, (3) reducing distances through land use policy measures, and (4) increasing efficiency and reducing environmental impacts through technological innovation.

To understand and plan the development of cities, it is necessary to study the relationships between transport infrastructure networks, land use and travel behaviour. The interrelated changes of these three components could directly and/or indirectly influence the economic, environmental and social performance of cities.

Urban transportation systems are designed to operate under defined conditions taking into account the connection with the land uses with the criteria of accessibility, capacity and efficiency. The academic literature shows that accessibility is a central factor between spatial structure and travel behaviour.

However, transport and land use systems face unprecedented challenges and uncertainties and are undergoing profound transformation, shaped by global environmental pressures, technological disruption, and changing socio-economic patterns, which influence the dynamic interactions between human behaviour, urban form, and mobility networks. Understanding these interactions is essential for developing transport-land use strategies capable of supporting resilient, sustainable, and even antifragile urban futures.

Deliverable D3.1 "*Analysis of the Transport network and Land use dynamics*" is the key output of Task T3.1 within Work Package 3 (WP3) of the **AntifragiCity project**. This task aims to analyse the connection between land use and transport networks as a fundamental concept for designing safe, efficient, sustainable, and resilient transport systems and to determine interdependent factors influencing transport-land use system dynamics. Land use and transport infrastructure are closely

interlinked, underpinned theoretically in the so-called transport land-use feedback cycle. Still, nowadays, cities are challenged to meet new goals based on Climate Neutral and Smart Cities Mission, the Urban Sustainability Goals and the Road Safety Goals while increasing resilience and capabilities to deal with future uncertainties.

Based on the findings of Tasks T2.1 and T2.5 and the KPIs of Task 2.7, the Deliverable 3.1 addresses three core objectives aligned with Task T3.1:

Objective 1: Analyse the transport network and land use dynamics in terms of current and future vulnerabilities, stressors and needs.

Objective 2: Provide the challenges and opportunities for evolving the transport land-use cycle analysing the policy, legislative and strategic frameworks.

Objective 3: Develop a holistic urban mobility dynamics model that aligns with the future challenges and promotes a human-driven perspective that supports future mobility needs and emergencies in line with land use and planning while minimizing the environmental impact.

2.2 Findings from other Deliverables

The Deliverable 3.1 takes into account findings and facts from the Deliverable D2.1 “Urban Event Mapping” and the Deliverable D2.5 “Ontology Framework”.

2.2.1 Findings from the Deliverable 2.1

From the analysis of the systematic literature review, conducted in the framework of D2.1, the disaster taxonomy affecting urban mobility includes five major domains:

- Natural, such as severe weather (e.g. rain, storm), hydrological (floods), or geophysical (earthquake) events
- Human-induced/social includes public disputes, terrorist attacks, or pandemics.
- Operational, such as traffic and transport accidents and emergencies.
- Technological/infrastructure includes power blackout, network outage, fuel shortage, or cyber-attacks.
- Systemic/structural issues, such as economic crises, inflation, or geopolitical (e.g. wars) events.

Concerning the time spectrum of the events, the categorization is the following:

Daily Stressors: traffic congestion, parking shortages, minor signal malfunctions. These events are frequent and short-lived but cumulatively erode mobility efficiency.

Mid-Scale Events: localised flooding, public protests affecting key transport corridors, strikes disrupting bus and metro services, moderate snowstorms. They require tactical responses such as rerouting and service headway adjustments.

Large-Scale Disruptions: major natural disasters (e.g., floods covering entire districts, earthquakes), widespread power outages and conflicts that damage transport infrastructure. They necessitate strategic interventions and long-term recovery.

The mobility, rather than being merely a functional outcome, serves as the primary adaptive mechanism through which urban systems respond to and learn from disruptions, mediating relationships between all other system components.

Focusing on urban environmental disruptions and how urban mobility system responds, the results reveal the need for holistic integrated responses to satisfy the property of resilience. System resilience emerges through mobility network reconfiguration rather than restoration.

The urban mobility systems exhibit antifragile characteristics when responding to disruptions, with 'mobility' functioning as the central organizing principle through which systems not only recover but potentially improve following disruptive events.

2.2.2 Findings from the Deliverable 2.5

In the Deliverable 2.5 the urban mobility system is dealt with as a cyber-physical system and as a socio-technical system.

Concerning the characterization of a cyber-physical system, urban mobility systems combine *physical components* (as infrastructure networks, vehicles, depots, signals, sensors), *cyber components* (control centres, edge computing nodes, analytics engines, digital platforms, communication networks and databases), and *sensing and actuation loops* (integrated sensor networks, traffic monitoring modules, incident detection processes and signalling controls).

The characterization of a socio-technical system:

- It involves **human actors and institutions**: citizens, operators, planners, regulators, emergency services and other agencies (Actor, Governance Instrument).
- It is shaped by **norms, regulations, policies and informal practices**: regulations, legal constraints, governance levels, data sharing agreements, roles and responsibilities.
- It is influenced by **behavioural responses** and **social vulnerability**: mode choice, route choice, behavioural nudges, incentives, inequities across social groups.

The concept of resilience and antifragility clearly explained in the Deliverable 2.5.:

Resilience is presented as the capacity to absorb shocks, adapt and return to an acceptable level of service within a reasonable time after a disruption.

Antifragility emphasises systems that benefit from variability, volatility and shocks. An antifragile urban mobility system is not merely capable of returning to its pre-disruption state; instead, it uses disruptions as opportunities to learn, adapt and improve its post-disruption state.

Conceptually, antifragility is characterised by:

- **Performance improvement after perturbations**: measurable increases in key performance indicators (e.g. accessibility, reliability, equity, emissions) after learning from disruptions;
- **Diversity of responses**: availability of multiple alternative routes, modes, governance mechanisms or interventions that can be selectively applied;
- **Sensitivity to signals**: the ability to detect weak signals, incipient problems and opportunities;
- **Adaptation of structure and rules**: capability to modify network configurations, service patterns, policies and behavioural incentives

The antifragility of an urban system as a cyber-physical system depends on:

- the **richness and reliability of sensing** (data quality, latency, provenance, trust);
- the **flexibility of actuation** (available measures, controllable signals, adaptable service configurations);
- the **robustness of communication and computation** (edge vs centralised processing, resilience to outages and cyber-attacks).

The antifragility of an urban system as a socio-technical system can be achieved through the combination of:

- **governance mechanisms** that can adapt policies and regulations in response to new information
- **participatory processes** that incorporate stakeholder feedback, consultation events and requirement refinement
- **behavioural interventions** and nudges that encourage more sustainable and robust mobility choices
- **equity and inclusiveness** as core objectives, ensuring that vulnerability and access disparities are reduced (equity groups, vulnerable areas, risk exposure).

2.3 Key Definitions

The definition of the core concepts, found in this Deliverable, are presented below:

Land use refers to the way urban land is functionally allocated, organized and regulated for specific human activities and built forms. It encompasses both the actual pattern of occupation (e.g. residential, commercial, industrial, institutional, recreational, transportation uses) and the normative framework (such as zoning and planning regulations) that governs the location, intensity and mixing of these activities within the urban fabric. Land use is commonly linked with demographic and economic attributes. The level of spatial accumulation of activities and their associated levels of mobility requirements.

Mobility relates to the total amount of travel that is undertaken on all forms of transport, and it includes the physical movement from one place to another. It covers both the movement of people and freight. As Cresswell (2010) says mobility is a socio-spatial experience and the method of movement shapes that experience (12).

Transport (verb) “to carry, convey or remove from one place or person to another”. Transport is broader than mobility and includes the modes of transport as well as the supply of transport through various institutions and organizations.

Transport and mobility are thus closely related and linked. These two concepts provide the links between our desire to move, to change our life situation, to fulfil our aspirations and to provide the means available to physically move. While the desire to move shapes our transportation system, it is the same time shaped by it.

John Urry (2007) defines the “**mobilities paradigm**” as a wide, more contested and ambiguous concept (44). Mobilities are a wide array of economic, social and political practices, infrastructures

and ideologies that all involve, entail or curtail various kinds of movement of people or ideas, information or objects.

Transport behaviour is the way people use the transport infrastructure networks to connect their activity locations. Different factors as trip length, distances, times, durations, travel modes, frequencies may change behaviour.

Transport infrastructure is important for physical movement to actually take place. So, mobility can be seen as being situated between the demand for transport and the infrastructure that allows this demand to be realized.

Spatial interactions, the nature, extent, origins, and destinations of the urban mobility of passengers and freight. They consider the attributes of the transport system and the land use factors generating and attracting movements.

Accessibility, as an essential concept in the transport, access to services/facilities depends on how transport is organized scale, or as the extent to which land-use and transport systems enable (groups of) individuals to reach activities or destinations by means of a (combination of) transport mode(s).

3 The Land Use-Transport system

3.1 Theory of Land-Use Transport Interaction

There has been much discussion about the relationship between the built environment and transport investment. The research of the factors that change the nexus between transport and development has been examined since the late of 1800s, where the early railway network infrastructure has been developed (14).

Today people are travelling farther to reach places of employment, education, health, leisure and other activities. The rapid increase in urban population and the expansion of cities create a growing demand for transport infrastructure, services and mobility levels. At the heart of the “land-use transport system” is the two-way relationship between mobility and transport.

Urban land use is characterized by heterogeneity due to the fact that economic, political, institutional or cultural factors are concentrated in the central areas, where peripheral areas have lower levels of accumulation attributed to residential areas.

Urban areas are characterized by social, cultural and economic activities taking place at separate locations forming an activity system including retailing, management, manufacturing or residence. These activities imply a set of relationships with other land uses and support residents’ everyday needs. This generates flows, including the mobility of people and supported by transport systems (37).

The combined transport and land-use system allows people to travel between activities locations (home, work, recreational locations, malls etc.). Additionally, it allows companies to transport goods in their several stages of production and distribution between related locations.

Transportation and land use interactions mostly consider the retroactive relationships between activities, which are related to land use, and accessibility, which is transportation related.

The diversity of urban activities in diverse urban contexts generate transport demands which supporting by the transport system, namely infrastructure and modes. Many times, the question arises: "Does land use generates transport demands, or does transport demand generates and shape urban land use?" The answer is not clear-cut, as the relationship between land use and transportation is bidirectional. The distribution of land uses within the city interacts with the geography of travel, since every journey has a starting point and a destination.

The land use and travels systems interact; locations for urbanization are developed based on the location of transport infrastructure and new infrastructure often follows new urbanization. This phenomenon is referred to in the literature as land use-transport interaction (LUTI).

Dieleman and Wegener (2004) distinguish three main categories of theories explaining the two-way interaction between transport and land-use: technical theories (urban mobility systems), economic theories (cities as markets), and social theories (society and urban space) (13).

According to the technical theories which focus on urban mobility systems, it is the technical conditions such as transport technology which guide the form and organisation of urban developments. Transport and land use co-develop and codetermine travel behaviour.

The second category, economic theories, take account of location costs, e.g. for firms or households in addition. A fundamental assumption is that locations with good accessibility are more attractive and have a higher market values than peripheral locations.

The third category, social theories, explain how cities are shaped as space is appropriated by individuals or groups to explain the development of cities.

So, in urban transport systems, a static view of land use has traditionally prevailed, where transport demand was determined solely by current land use. New approaches in the field of transport and urban planning recognise that interventions in transport infrastructure can dynamically influence the distribution of land use. For example, the construction of a new metro station can increase demand for development around the station, as businesses and residents seek to take advantage of the increased accessibility. In addition, property and business values around metro stations increase significantly. The same is true for other forms of transport and transport infrastructure, such as motorways, intercity terminals, transfer stations, and urban multimodal passenger transport, etc.

The basic principle in urban transport design is to ensure accessibility, i.e. the ability of residents to move easily from their homes to other land uses, such as workplaces, shops, schools, entertainment venues, etc. (25). High-accessibility zones, where there are good connections to public transport and other transport infrastructure, are often the most desirable for urban development. Conversely, areas with low accessibility face problems of economic development and social cohesion. There is a scale effect at play in this relationship as large infrastructure projects tend to precede and trigger land-use changes. In contrast, small-scale transportation projects tend to complement the existing land use pattern. Further, the expansion of urban land use takes place over various circumstances such as infilling (near the city centre) or sprawl (far from the city centre) and where transportation plays a different role. For infilling, land value becomes high enough to justify developments despite potential congestion, while for sprawl, accessibility has improved enough (37).

The needs of people and their desired activities have an impact on their location choices and destinations and influenced by the provided transport infrastructure system. An increasing number of academic studies highlight the need to understand how mobility cultures are formed and created through social norms, identity, and equality and by different forms of transport.

Banister et al (2011), highlight the importance of societal values and aspirations to travel but also the need for technological solutions in the provision of infrastructure in the search of sustainable travel (8).

In the academic literature, the wider rationale of travel has been connected with attitudes to travel, namely, whether particular location decisions are associated with certain travel behaviours or whether people with particular types of attitude are attracted to certain urban forms (39). Theories such utility theory or socio-psychological theory examines the role and formation of travel habits. For example, utility theory provides a strong perspective for viewing alternative choices and evaluating

their costs and benefits, whereas socio-psychological theories examine the role of norms, attitudes and intentions associated with travel choices and behaviours.

It is interesting to analyse the need for changing mobility habits of people because of issues such as expansion of cities, climate change or any type of disruptions.

3.2 Land-use transport feedback cycle

The recognition that travel and location decisions interact and determine each other led to the principle of the 'land-use transport feedback cycle', as presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The “land-use transport feedback cycle”, revised from Wegener & Fuerst (2004) (46)

The set of the relationships derived by the cycle can be briefly summarised as follows:

- The distribution of different land-uses co-determines where activities (e.g. living, working, recreating) take place.
- The spatial distribution of activities creates the need for a transport system that offers people and goods the opportunity to travel or be transported from one activity to the other.
- In turn, ‘the distribution of infrastructure in the transport system combined with existing land-use patterns creates opportunities for spatial interaction and can be measured as accessibility’.
- Finally, the quality of accessibility co-determines where different types of land-uses are developed, which then influences the spatial distribution of activities and starts the cycle again.

The transport-land use feedback cycle describes the dynamic, two-way relationship between the transport system and land use. It is a framework that explains how changes in transport infrastructure (a new or improved one) improves accessibility, due to the fact that time or monetary cost of reaching certain locations is reduced. The change of the accessibility influence land use patterns, redistributing the locations of activities. Activity patterns are translated into travel behaviour as they take place over the existing transport system. Finally, change in travel behaviour will eventually demand new or improved transport infrastructure.

The transport-land use cycle is based on three main causal relationship:

- Accessibility as a key driver of location: The improvement of transport networks and infrastructure (e.g. new roads, railways, public transport networks) increases the attractiveness of areas and the ability to access jobs and services. Accessibility indicators, whether simple (e.g. cumulative opportunities) or complex (e.g. logsum measures from discrete choice models), enter location, development and land-price equations (19).
- Spatial equilibrium of land and transport markets: Increased accessibility raises the demand for development and higher density around transport hubs. Land and transport markets adjust (sometimes gradually, sometimes in assumed equilibria) such that no agent has an incentive to relocate, given prices, travel costs and constraints (11).
- Random utility and behavioural choice: Land uses and the overall spatial configuration influence mode choice, as compact and mixed-use areas favour public transport, cycling and walking instead of private cars (9).

Its durability stems from this tight logic and its usefulness as a framing device for integrated planning. By the critical analysis of the cycle some issues may arise:

- 1) The cycle centres accessibility, not mobility, as the mechanism linking spatial form, activity patterns and network performance. And this parameter contributes to the planning practice.
- 2) There are many exogenous factors which influence the performance of the cycle, such as new technological innovations, policy measures aims on economic growth, sustainable mobility policies, physical, socio-demographics, economic and policy changes.

- 3) Due to the complex interaction among several subsystems, the process of change in the overall urban environment is difficult to track and disentangle in both space and time. It takes time to observe the effect of change in one component of the cycle, on the other components. Responses of one change rates over time.
- 4) By asserting two-way causality, the model recognizes urban dynamics as cumulative and history-dependent. In practice, many long-run outcomes, e.g. corridor intensification after a major transit investment, are better understood as sequences of adjustments rather than one-off shocks.
- 5) The framework helps planners visualize why single-sector interventions (only roads, only zoning) often disappoint. The framework of the cycle can also be used when translated into empirical claims or modelling practice.
- 6) The systems of transport and land-use do not exist in isolation, but in wider economic and environmental contexts (Figure 2).

Figure 2. A conceptual model showing the components the land-use transport system, (by Allanfield Consulting , 2024) (6)

3.3 Land-use/transport interaction (LUTI) models

Land-use/transport interaction (LUTI) models provide formal representations of the bidirectional feedback between transport and land use. They have become key tools in strategic urban and transport planning, especially for ex-ante assessment of major infrastructure, pricing, and regulatory interventions. LUTI models are relevant not only as forecasting tools but also as conceptual frameworks that make explicit how changes in travel times, costs or reliability, can propagate into long-term land-use changes and spatial reorganisation of activities.

For more than six decades, urban researchers have sought to formalize this relationship using mathematical, statistical, and logical methods, and to produce models capable of predicting changes to transportation and land use systems as the result of policy measures. LUTI models have evolved from relatively simple, aggregate allocation schemes coupled to four-stage transport models to sophisticated microsimulation and agent-based platforms.

Different models embody different theoretical traditions (spatial interaction theory, random utility theory, urban economics, spatial equilibrium) and make distinct trade-offs between behavioural realism, spatial and temporal resolution, transparency, data requirements and computational burden.

3.3.1 Main modelling frameworks

A widely used way to classify LUTI models is by their level of aggregation and dominant modelling paradigm. Iacono et al (2008) distinguish three broad families: aggregate spatial-interaction models, econometric and spatial regression models, and disaggregate microsimulation/agent-based models (20). Acheampong and Silva (2004) provide a similar taxonomy, but explicitly organized around “generations” of LUTI models and the operational systems that exemplify each generation (1).

(a) Aggregate spatial-interaction / Lowry-type models

The first generation of integrated LUTI models, were based on the combination of Lowry model and four-step model approaches to represent the spatial interaction of land use and transportation. The model developed by Lowry was a spatial interaction model designed to simulate patterns of residential and service location in the Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania. The Lowry Model assumed the location of basic employment exogenously and generated an equilibrium for the allocation of non-basic employment and population (30). This model and its extensions, represents land-use and transport systems at a zonal level in terms of flows of residents, jobs and trips between zones.

The four-step model has become the traditional tool for forecasting demand and evaluating performance of transportation systems and large-scale transport infrastructure projects. It consists of four distinct steps of trip generation, trip distribution, modal split, and route assignment. Travel is modelled using trips as the unit of analysis based on origin-destination (O-D) survey. The spatial unit within which trips occur is represented as a number of aggregate traffic analysis zones (TAZ) defined based on socio-economic, demographic, and land-use characteristics.

Accessibility as a key driver of location, which measures the situation of a location relative to other activities or opportunities distributed in space. The utility of locations to households and firms

depends strongly on the ease of reaching jobs, markets, services and amenities. Accessibility indicators—whether simple (e.g. cumulative opportunities) or complex (e.g. logsum measures from discrete choice models)—enter location, development and land-price equations.

It is a “top-down” modelling framework, since the interaction between transportation modelling and utility of locations is based on the behaviour of a representative individual.

A residential location sub-model, allocating households to zones based on accessibility and capacity. Spatial-interaction (gravity) equations allocate activities and trips as functions of generalized cost, often derived from a separate four-stage model. Land-use change is typically modelled through relatively simple allocation routines that respond to accessibility and capacity constraints.

A trip-generation and distribution submodel, often using gravity-type equations of the form:

$$T_{ij} = A_i B_j O_i D_j f(c_{ij}),$$

where T_{ij} is the flow between zones i and j , O_i and D_j are productions and attractions, and $f(c_{ij})$ is a deterrence function of generalised cost. A_i and B_j are balancing factors that ensure the model satisfies both constraints.

Several models extended the basic Lowry framework in new directions:

TOMM (Time Oriented Metropolitan Model, developed by Crecine 1964), disaggregation of the population; incorporation of inertia effects in activity allocation

PLUM (developed by Goldner, 1971), a replaced standard gravity model with intervening opportunity model; use of county-specific dispersion parameters.

ITLUP (The Integrated Transportation and Land Use Package developed by Putman, 1991, 1998) is the first complete software package for integrated modelling; improved calibration techniques; improved network model with multiple modes; incorporation of congestion effects in activity allocation.

LILT (Leeds Integrated Land-Use/Transport model developed by Mackett, 1983) use of accessibility function; car ownership submodel; land use model capable of handling demolition, changing occupancy and vacancy rates.

IRPUD (the model of the Dortmund region developed by Wegener, 1982) contains seven separate submodels; microsimulation of land use; use of differing spatial scales for submodels; separates discretionary and non-discretionary travel.

These models are attractive for regional and national scenario analysis because they can incorporate economic linkages and are easier to embed in official appraisal frameworks.

However, aggregate models also have significant limitations:

- represent behaviour at a highly aggregated level (flows and averages rather than individual decisions); they generally do not model individual households or firms
- often assume smooth adjustment towards equilibrium, underplaying path dependence, lock-in development processes; they may rely on equilibrium assumptions that are poorly suited to representing path-dependent urban development or non-marginal shifts such as disruptive technologies and radical policy changes.

- may struggle to represent fine-scale spatial outcomes (e.g. corridor densification, node-place interactions at specific intersections) that are critical in urban design and safety analysis
- most were static equilibrium models incapable of capturing the dynamics of urban systems
- none of the models actually represented land markets with explicit prices; zones were highly aggregate and lacked spatial detail, and the models were inadequately supported by theory. Inadequate theory may have also been a reason that many of the models forecasted so poorly.

(b) Econometric and spatial regression models

Developments in the use of random utility theory to describe choices among the alternatives, such as the choice of travel mode provided the development of econometric approach models.

Land use and transportation models that follow econometric frameworks can be thought of as comprising two types of models: regional economic models and land market models. In these two types of simulation models the economic model and the land market model each form the core of a simulation system that includes the prediction of transportation flows. Both types tend to have improved representation of land markets that include endogenously determined (determined within the model) prices and market clearing mechanisms.

Typical applications include:

- Hedonic price and rent models, where land or housing prices are regressed on structural, locational and accessibility attributes.
- Discrete choice models of residential or firm location, where the probability of choosing a zone depends on accessibility and other zone characteristics.
- Spatial regression models (spatial lag / spatial error) that explicitly account for spatial dependence in densities, development probabilities or land values.

These models are often integrated with transport models, for example by: computing accessibility indicators from a network assignment or activity-based model; using these as explanatory variables in land-use regressions; then feeding back predicted land-use changes into updated travel-demand forecasts.

The most used models are:

MEPLAN, (Integrated modelling package developed by Marcial Echenique, 1969, 1990) the incorporation of the spatial input-output model with economic evaluation component; able to forecast commercial trip generation; travel treated as a derived demand.

TRANUS, (the transport and land-use model developed by de la Barra, 1989), a development supply model which simulates choices of developers; sophisticated travel model with combined mode-route choice.

MUSSA, (the '5-Stage Land-Use Transport Model' developed by Martinez for Santiago de Chile, 1992), the incorporation of bid-rent framework for land, floor space markets; detailed representation of transit network in travel model; high level of household type disaggregation.

METROSIM, (the microeconomic land-use and transport model developed by Anas, 1994), a model extended to commercial real estate markets; addition of dynamic CHPMM housing market model.

DELTA, (the new land-use modelling package DELTA by Davids Simmonds Consultancy, Cambridge, 1999), a microsimulation of demographic changes; treatment of quality in the market for space.

PECAS, (Production, Exchange, and Consumption Allocation, System, developed by Hunt and Abraham, 2005), a regional econometric model with microsimulation of land development at the parcel level; ability to couple with an activity-based travel model and to apply at supra-regional level.

The econometric models succeeded in incorporating the behavioural theory into urban modelling, which was not taken into account by aggregate models.

Despite these advancements, many of the econometric models retained a number of limitations:

- they remained highly aggregate, despite the use of disaggregate calibration methods. This became one source of bias in the model forecasts.
- all of the models were essentially static in nature. Their structure forced them to reach a general equilibrium between each time step in the model; this was especially true of the models focusing on land markets.
- little advancement was made in the transportation component of the model. Most models continued to use trip-based, four-step forecasting procedures, where all submodels except mode choice were run at an aggregate level.
- they typically lack an explicit representation of complex market mechanisms, they may not fully capture feedbacks between land and transport, and their predictive validity outside the estimation context can be limited.

c) Microsimulation models

Advances in computing power and efficiency of data storage have as a result the development of models that address many of the shortcomings of the previous models.

Microsimulation models are particularly effective for modelling systems that are dynamic and complex as urban system is.

The basic conceptual element of these models is that they attempt to represent processes of change from the bottom up, taking into account the behaviour of individuals agents in space and time, along with interactions between agents.

Recent models related to the microsimulation include activity-based models of travel behaviour, multi-agent models of urban land use and transportation, and cell-based models of urban land use. Activity-based models attempt to simulate travel behaviour within the limits of time and space.

ILUTE (developed by Salvani and Miller, 2005) comprehensive urban system microsimulation model; structured to accurately capture temporal elements urban change; activity-travel model includes household member interactions; disequilibrium modelling framework.

UrbanSim (developed by Waddell, 2003), the new microeconomic model of location choice of households and firms; it simulates individual households, jobs, developers and parcels, each following probabilistic decision rules (e.g. location choice, development choice) estimated from observed data using discrete-choice models. Transport interaction is represented by accessibility metrics derived from an external travel-demand model, and land-use outcomes feedback to transport via changes in trip origins and destinations. Accessibility measures from an external travel-demand model (four-stage or activity-based) enter these decision rules; in turn, the spatial redistribution of households and jobs affects subsequent travel-demand forecasts.

Although the evolution of technology helps the modelling, there are some reasons that explain the slow adoption of activity-based models:

- activity-based models are fraught with the challenges of huge data requirements and uncertainty associated with the micro-simulation methodology used.
- the demand for high-quality data, making model development and calibration very difficult tasks
- detailed data on activity participation and mobility patterns at the individual level are expensive and time consuming to be conducted independently.
- the use of sensor technology as GPS in mobile phones raises a number of privacy concerns and could meet opposition.
- the long execution time involved in running models

3.3.2 Critical analysis of the cycle framework

All the types of LUTI models (aggregate-spatial, econometric and microsimulation model) seek to represent the co-evolution of land-use patterns and transport system performance through feedback loops: transport performance shapes accessibility; accessibility influences location and development; land use outcomes reshape travel demand and network conditions.

Except of the fundamental feedback loop the LUTI models have to explain: a) how causality is inferred within it, b) how constraints and institutions are represented, c) how uncertainty is handled and communicated.

From the analysis of the models, from academic research papers, some common points for consideration:

1. Despite differences in conformity, most LUTI models embed some combination of accessibility theory as a central explanatory construct, spatial equilibrium logic (explicitly or implicitly) and behavioural choice (stated as utility-based).
2. Although real-world location choices are driven by institutional constraints, housing market structure, regulations and social networks, the *accessibility* plays main role in models as it is measurable and model-friendly parameter.
3. The models face the same fundamental question: whose behaviour is being represented and under what conditions. Households and firms are typically assumed to respond to changes in accessibility. The supply mechanisms is often simplified.
4. Land-use-transport interaction (LUTI) models have long faced limitations linked to (a) theoretical assumptions, (b) data and calibration constraints, and (c) the representation of behaviour and spatial mechanisms.
5. They frequently rely on equilibrium logics and “representative” agents (households/firms), thereby underestimating heterogeneity, bounded rationality, inertia and adjustment delays (time lags), and non-linearities in land and real-estate market adaptation.

6. Supply-side processes (development dynamics, planning regulations, developer behaviour, financing) are often modelled more crudely than demand, resulting in a weaker depiction of capacity constraints, regulatory regimes, and price/rent dynamics
7. Methodologically, strong parameter sensitivity, identifiability issues, uncertainty propagation across coupled submodels (travel–accessibility–location–prices), and dependence on historical data can produce risks of “false precision,” particularly when models are applied outside the calibration domain or to policies that structurally alter the system.
8. Many LUTI models presume that the system tends toward a stable configuration after a policy shock. However, real urban systems do not have the same reaction and sometimes there are persistent disequilibrium, regulatory discontinuities and political decisions. These types of reactions are reinforced by the time scale responses of changes.
9. Models typically approximate land use and housing markets with simplified price functions or proxies for attractiveness. This often underestimates market and institutional price formation.
10. Transport changes can affect travel times quickly while land-use responses may take years or decades, which the modules often compress these dynamics into simplified adjustment rules. So, the model does not capture short-run responsiveness to transport interventions or long-run lock-in driven by legacy infrastructure and neighborhood trajectory.

3.3.3 Future challenges and vulnerabilities

The next generation of LUTI models must shift from largely static forecasts toward robust, dynamic, and uncertainty-aware decision-support tools capable of capturing new challenges.

Alipour and Dia (2023), in their paper, stresses the need a LUTI model for integrating environmental and energy considerations into land use and transportation to achieve sustainability (Figure 3) (3). They also confirm the role of sustainable mobility in social, environmental and engineering factors in the energy debate. While the topics of fundamental studies that formed the direction of this research such as policy integration, sustainable accessibility, and travel behaviour analysis are still subjects of interest, the trend is shifting towards more active transport, transit-oriented development, and advanced simulations at the micro-level.

Rapid technological and societal change, technological transition to AVs and electrification, digital dependencies, and climate adaptation challenges, all of them deeply affect how land use and transport co-evolve.

New dynamics in the future introduce additional vulnerabilities:

1. Incorporating emerging mobility systems (MaaS, micromobility, shared services, connected and automated vehicles) with realistic representations of cost, reliability, comfort, and travel-time variability. More reliance on digital platforms creates “single points of failure”.

2. Treat equity as endogenous by incorporating affordability constraints, neighbourhood transition mechanisms, accessibility to essential services as healthcare, education.
3. Behavioural response in new mobility regimes. Mobility services may exclude those without digital literacy. Aging populations may demand more accessible, local and non-motorized mobility.
4. New models scenario frameworks that vary explicitly the drivers of telework, e-commerce, service restructuring, and activity reallocation processes that structurally reshape travel demand and the value of accessibility.
5. Coupling with climate, energy and risk dimensions (urban heat, flooding, network resilience) as endogenous drivers, so that land-use projections align with decarbonization and adaptation objectives.
6. Explicitly quantifying uncertainty (scenario analysis, Bayesian/ensemble approaches, stress testing) rather than producing single-scenario “certain” estimates.
7. Stronger integration of the supply side (developers, financial constraints, regulatory controls) and distributional impacts is required so that policies are evaluated not only for average efficiency but also for fairness and accessibility for vulnerable groups.
8. Leveraging “new” data sources (mobile-phone data, sensors, smart cards) must be accompanied by transparent data governance, privacy protection, model interpretability, and reproducible calibration, ensuring LUTI models remain scientifically credible and institutionally usable in real planning processes.

Figure 3. Conceptual framework of integrating energy and environmental factors in LUTI methodologies to achieve sustainability (by Dorsa Alipour and Hussein Dia (2023) (3)

4 Policy, Legislative, Strategic Frameworks

4.1 Introduction

European policy on transport and spatial development is embedded within an integrated set of strategies and objectives aimed at the transition toward climate-neutral, resilient, and sustainable cities. The EU has set a long-term target of full climate neutrality by 2050 and interim targets of 55% and 90% net emissions reductions by 2030 and 2040, respectively, compared with 1990 levels (climate.ec.europa.eu). To ensure these goals are achieved and legally binding, the EU has assembled a coherent institutional ecosystem that seeks to transform the way transport, energy, and land uses interact, linking climate, transport, and spatial development.

Transport lies at the heart of the European policy, with concrete targets to deliver a sustainable and resilient system by promoting low-emission transport and more compact spatial forms. The transition toward low-carbon mobility, integrated urban development, and climate-resilient infrastructure, enrich both sustainability and resilience outcomes.

Fundamental concept is the transformation of the transport-land use system towards a more sustainable framework highlighting the positive loop of the interaction as: compact cities with good public transport → reduced car dependency → cleaner, more resilient urban environments.

The policy, legislative, strategic frameworks below are examined in the direction to how they embed concepts such as resilience and sustainability and how they connect to the feedback loop between transport and land use.

The policy frameworks that are examined are:

1. European Green Deal
2. “Fit to 55” Package
3. Mission for Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities
4. Road Safety Goals
5. Urban Sustainability Goals and UN SDGs

4.2 European Green Deal

Main goal: The European Green Deal is essentially the EU’s primary strategy to become economically self-reliant and competitive. Its goal is to gradually turn the EU into the world’s first climate-neutral continent by 2050. Proposed by Commission President Ursula von der Leyen in 2019, it aims by 2030 to achieve a 50–55% reduction in emissions and sets the binding objective of full neutrality by 2050,

as noted above. The legal basis ensuring the binding nature of this long-term goal is the European Climate Law (Regulation (EU) 2021/1119 of 30 June 2021).

The Green Deal spans all sectors of the economy, including transport, energy, agriculture, and buildings, with action proposals for climate, the environment, and clean energy. Given that transport accounts for 5% of EU GDP and employs over 10 million people in Europe, its importance for European businesses and global supply chains is evident.

The Green Deal is directly related to the land use–transport system and explicitly frames resilience and sustainability as core objectives, even if it is not a technical land-use/transport modelling framework. It establishes an economy-wide decarbonisation pathway in which transport is treated as a priority sector and is linked to spatial planning outcomes through its emphasis on compact, efficient, and low-emission urban system. A core ambition is to reduce greenhouse-gas emissions from transport by 90% by 2050—a highly ambitious target considering that transport currently accounts for 25% of the EU’s total emissions and has been on an upward trajectory in recent years.

Transport-Land use feedback: Indicative pathways toward sustainable mobility include:

- (a) reducing dependence on fossil fuels by accelerating the uptake of zero-emission vehicles and renewable fuels;
- (b) promoting alternatives to private car use by doubling high-speed rail traffic and further developing cycling infrastructure;
- (c) more efficient and equitable transport pricing via carbon pricing and user incentives;
- (d) greening freight transport.

In land use–transport terms, the Green Deal’s logic is that emissions reductions and accessibility gains are achieved not only through cleaner vehicles and fuels, but also by changing demand patterns—supporting modal shift to public transport, walking and cycling, strengthening rail and multimodal freight, and encouraging urban development forms that reduce trip lengths and car dependence.

For smart mobility, critical levers include the use of data and artificial intelligence, and the achievement of automated, multimodal mobility with the full replacement of conventional tickets by smart electronic ones usable across multiple modes. This implies a broader restructuring of the urban structure that also affects land use. The promotion of multimodal systems, rail corridors, and automated electric vehicles leads to a new balance between accessibility and development density.

Resilience: On resilience, the Green Deal promotes systemic risk reduction by accelerating energy diversification, improving the efficiency of infrastructure and networks, and embedding climate adaptation into investment decisions. So, resilience is framed as energy and economic stability: energy resilience via the phase-out of fossil fuels and expansion of renewables; supply-chain resilience via a transfer for a circular economy and diversification of raw-material sources; strengthening the single market via completion of the Trans-European Transport Network (TEN-T); and achieving equitable, safe, and fair mobility.

The Deal also stresses infrastructure resilience. Transport is vulnerable to disruptions—as evidenced by the unprecedented public-health crisis at the start of this decade due to COVID-19. The EU responded with measures such as “Green Lanes” to maintain supply chains and support schemes across transport modes.

Overall, the Green Deal explicitly embeds resilience via adaptation policies, investment in resilient infrastructure, and network upgrades so the system can absorb shocks and recover quickly.

Sustainability: On sustainability, the Green Deal is totally aligned: the direction of the environmental sustainability through net-zero targets and pollution reduction. It also satisfies social sustainability via the transformation of the land-use and transport measures (e.g., low-emission zones, pricing, network reallocation), which measures must be accompanied by equitable accessibility and affordability.

4.3 “Fit for 55” Package

Main goal: “Fit for 55” (European Commission, 2021) is a comprehensive set of legislative proposals designed to enable the EU to achieve at least a 55% reduction in greenhouse-gas emissions by 2030. It revises and updates EU laws—such as the Emissions Trading System (Directive 2003/87/EC), the Energy Efficiency Directive (Directive (EU) 2023/1791), and the Renewable Energy Directive (Directive (EU) 2018/2001)—to align the framework with the overarching objective of climate neutrality by 2050. The package consists of interlinked proposals balancing pricing, targets, standards, and support measures.

Transport-Land use feedback: The measures directly influence how cities organize mobility. Through economic incentives, regulatory pressure, and more effective spatial planning, the package “Fit for 55” seeks a gradual shift away from private car dependence toward more reliable public transport which spatial planning is re-oriented. While the transition will take time, the transport-land-use feedback loop sits at the centre of the framework.

It also targets the transport energy transition via enabling measures such as the Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation (AFIR), which shape where and how charging/refuelling infrastructure is deployed across cities and corridors—thereby interacting with land-use patterns, logistics locations, and multimodal hubs.

Resilience: From a resilience perspective, Fit for 55 strengthens system robustness primarily through diversification and efficiency: higher renewables and energy-efficiency requirements reduce exposure to fossil-fuel volatility and improve the adaptive capacity of urban systems and critical infrastructure, which is directly relevant to transport networks that depend on secure energy supply and climate-ready assets. Systems with multiple, distinct travel choices can withstand and recover more rapidly from disruptions such as fuel shortages, energy crises, or supply-chain problems. EU climate-neutrality initiatives thus extend beyond decarbonization to include resilience. However, the most effective long-term disruption requires planning for dense, mixed-use communities to reduce the need to travel, thereby strengthening the positive transport land use feedback cycle.

Sustainability: From a sustainability perspective, the package is explicitly designed to deliver emissions reductions cost-effectively while emphasising a socially fair transition.

4.4 Mission for Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities

Main goal: The EU Mission for Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities (“Cities Mission”) aims to achieve 100 climate-neutral cities by 2030 that will act as innovation and experimentation hubs for all European cities by 2050. Participating cities must develop Climate City Contracts, co-created with stakeholders, outlining action plans and investment strategies for climate neutrality across energy, transport, waste management, and buildings.

Transport-Land use feedback: The Mission is tightly connected to the land use-transport system. The Climate City Contract (its core implementation instrument) requires cities to co-produce an integrated pathway and an accompanying investment plan, typically spanning sectors that directly structure land-use/transport dynamics (mobility, energy, buildings, waste) and the governance arrangements needed to deliver them.

In land use–transport terms, this contract-based approach pushes cities toward accessibility-led decarbonisation e.g., shifting trips to public transport and active modes, reorganising logistics, deploying charging and digital mobility infrastructure, and aligning spatial development with lower-carbon travel demand. The Mission’s objective is not only cleaner vehicles but citywide net-zero outcomes that depend on the urban form and the performance of transport networks.

Resilience: The Mission treats climate neutrality and resilience as two sides of the same coin, highlighting resilience’s dual dimensions: climatic/energetic and social/operational. Through Climate City Contracts, cities generate documents and know-how (via the Mission Platform/NetZeroCities and related finance-focused mechanisms) to ensure sustainable mobility even during crises or disasters—so a disruption in one sector (e.g., energy grid damage) does not cascade into total system failure (e.g., transport collapse). Resilience emerges as fundamental to transport systems and as achievable through effective land-use transport which improves cities’ ability to manage transition risks, infrastructure dependencies, and shocks that can disrupt urban mobility and services.

Sustainability: the Mission is an applied pathway to climate mitigation at urban scale, promoting integrated solutions that simultaneously reduce emissions, improve air quality and energy efficiency, and accelerate the “twin” green–digital transition in cities—outcomes that are inherently shaped by how land uses and transport systems are planned, operated, and funded.

4.5 EU’s Road Safety Goals

Main goal: The EU’s Road Safety Policy (2021–2030) has a long-term strategic goal of zero fatalities and zero serious injuries by 2050 (“Vision Zero”), with a mid-term target to halve both by 2030 (relative to 2019). At its heart lies the Safe System approach, which accepts that human error is inevitable and calls for a forgiving road environment.

Transport-Land use feedback: Although focused on fatalities, the philosophy is tightly linked to land use: urban-design elements such as lower speed limits (e.g. 30km/h in cities), pedestrian- and cyclist-friendly infrastructure for vulnerable users, and reallocation of road space support dense, multimodal, and safer cities, are a direct tool to manage the consequences of the transport system within dense urban land use.

In practice, this aligns with land-use/transport planning choices such as allocating street space, designing junctions and corridors, and prioritising safer modes (public transport, walking, cycling) in urban areas—interventions that change accessibility patterns and therefore influence travel demand and spatial development.

Resilience: The policy’s emphasis on safer speeds, forgiving road design, and improved post-crash response increases the transport system’s capacity to absorb shocks (collisions and their cascading disruption) and recover faster, which is a functional resilience attribute for urban mobility networks.

Sustainability: Road safety is a precondition for sustainable urban design and is a critical input into the land-use side of the feedback loop. Re-balance streets toward safer active and shared modes support healthier, more liveable urban environments can reinforce sustainability goals.

4.6 United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Main goal: The EU is fully committed to the 2030 Agenda and the 17 SDGs which provide a global framework for sustainable development. The SDGs are a direct and widely used reference framework for analysing land use–transport system linkages, as well as resilience and sustainability, because they define internationally agreed objectives and measurable targets that explicitly cover urban form, mobility access, safety, infrastructure performance, and climate risk.

Of particular relevance is SDG 11: “Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable,” closely aligned with EU initiatives such as the Cities Mission and tied to European urban policy.

Two critical targets highlight the transport-land use link:

- Target 11.2: “provide access to safe, affordable, accessible and sustainable transport systems for all”
- Target 11.3: “enhance inclusive and sustainable urbanization and capacity for participatory, integrated and sustainable human settlement planning and management”.

SDG Target 3.6, “By 2020, halve the number of global deaths and injuries from road traffic accidents”, is directly relevant to the land use–transport system because it frames road traffic injury as a public-health outcome that is materially determined by how cities allocate space, manage speeds, and design networks and junctions—i.e., by land-use patterns (trip lengths, exposure, concentration of activity) and transport system design (mode share, street hierarchy, safe crossings, separation of vulnerable road users).

The EU’s pursuit of urban sustainability directly supports this goal. Sub-targets explicitly refer to equitable access to safe, affordable, and accessible transport systems and call for integrated and sustainable spatial planning. The UN highlights the negative impacts of urban sprawl, which undermines sustainable development by increasing CO₂ emissions and inequalities. Consequently, the EU’s urban-sustainability drive runs through integrated spatial planning: promoting compact, mixed-use cities with strong public transport to counter negative transport–land-use feedbacks.

5 Integrated Urban mobility models

5.1 Introduction

Contemporary land-use and transport planning increasingly gives priority to satisfying the accessibility rather than mobility, reflecting a shift from optimizing travel speeds to optimizing the ease of reaching opportunities and activities.

Within this paradigm, the 15-minute city and Transit-Oriented Development (TOD) have gained prominence as spatial strategies intended to reduce car dependence, address climate and public health externalities, and remediate inequities in access to services and employment.

The **15-minute city** conceptualizes urban resilience and quality of life through **proximity**, the distribution of daily needs within short travel times, typically by walking, cycling, and local public transport, thereby targeting reductions in trip length, household transport cost burdens, and “time poverty” associated with dispersed urban form (31).

Transit-Oriented Development, by contrast, focuses on aligning **density**, **land-use mix**, and **pedestrian-friendly station** catchments with high-capacity transit to increase ridership, improve service viability, and channel growth into compact corridors and nodes, addressing the structural mismatch between sprawled development patterns and efficient mass transit provision (10).

5.2 15-min city model

5.2.1 The model

Over the last few years, the idea of the ‘15-minute city’ has spread rapidly among urban policy makers and politicians. This term is originally attributed to Carlos Moreno (Urbanist Professor of Sorbonne). Triggered by the COVID-19 crisis, the 15-min city concept has emerged as a new model of city vision. This increasingly popular urban planning paradigm brings the idea of living locally at the forefront of city planning, aiming to alleviate the intense urban challenges. Moreno envisioned dense and connected socially and functionally mixed neighbourhoods based on the human scale design to encourage walking and cycling (34).

The concept of the 15-minute city is one of the most prominent attempts to avoid or shorten trips in people's everyday lives. This can be achieved if essential services (e.g. shops, pharmacies, schools,

work places, hospitals, leisure destinations etc.) are physically close to people's residential bases. The concept is thus tightly linked to spatial planning strategies and places strong emphasis on neighbourhood-based planning (31), (32) (Figure 4).

The concept incorporates four basic dimensions: (1) density, (2) proximity, (3) diversity, and (4) digitization.

Essentially, it promotes the creation of neighbourhoods with an optimal number of people, a mix of uses and quick access to basic services, while ensuring cultural and social diversity (5), (32).

Figure 4. Conceptual model of the 15-Minute City

Emphasis is placed on the neighbourhood as a key element of spatial and functional organization, and thus cities should be organized into neighbourhoods within which every need can be met within a 15-minute walk or bike ride (22), (36). Beyond proximity, other important design principles include enhanced land use mix, optimizing land use by allowing multiple functions in one place, and diverse and affordable housing options. In this context, the concept of proximity relies on the use of open data, digitization, geolocation systems, and the massification of new services. The visionary result is the development of integrated, self-sufficient neighbourhoods designed to provide citizens with safe and convenient access to the necessities of their daily lives.

The 15-minute city is a human-centric concept. Instead of viewing movement solely as a demand derived from the need to get from A to B, it underpins the importance of the quality of the living environment through which people move, i.e. a safe, clean, inclusive and pleasant environment that stimulates people's senses of place, community and belonging and fosters social interactions. As such, the 15-minute city can positively influence the liveability of urban spaces and the well-being of their inhabitants (32).

Pozoukidou & Chatziyiannaki (2021), in their research examine the wider context by three key concepts, three evaluation pillars: inclusion, safety and health (35). Each pillar contains an number of indicators which they describe the core pillar.

Figure 5. Illustration of the 15-minute Paris (Source: Carlos Moreno, (31))

Table 1: Dimensions constitute the 15-minute city (based on literature review)

Proximity	A proximity-oriented strategy that focuses on the redistribution and relocation of urban amenities and resources within neighbourhoods.
Density	Density can provide a critical mass for the operation of local services and businesses within walking distances
Diversity	Creating multi-use neighbourhoods that include residential, commercial and recreational uses
Digitalization	Smart technologies enable planners to access real-time and timely data, help citizens participate more actively in planning and decision-making processes
Human scale urban design	The scale and form of a 15-min. city are defined based on human needs and characteristics
Connectivity	Within 15-min. city neighbourhoods, active mobility modes like walking and cycling are combined with public transportation, increasing public transportation efficiency, and addressing first/last mile connections
Flexibility	The 15-min. city concept advocates the transformation of single-function public and semi-public spaces into multi-purpose areas to maximize the utilization of buildings and spaces

The implementation of the concept of 15-min. city is associated with the contribution to *urban sustainability*, reducing environmental burdens by limiting the structural drivers of carbon mobility. Basic policies are proximity-oriented development, compact and mixed-use urban structures, reallocation of street space away of private vehicles, strengthening active mobility and public transport conditions.

The framework may also strengthen social *resilience* by supporting local public spaces and community infrastructure that facilitate social interaction and mutual support, which are recognised as important capacities during crises. Finally, proximity strategies often create opportunities for *climate adaptation* co-benefits by enabling street redesigns that incorporate urban greening, shade, and stormwater management—measures that reduce heat exposure and flood risk.

However, given the diversity of urban spaces and their inhabitants, there are many open questions about how the concept can be adapted to different urban contexts and how it addresses aspects of justice and equity, taking into account the needs and capacities of different social groups. Risks of gentrification and displacement or uneven service distribution are concerns for consideration. Adaptability and flexibility in urban planning strategies are essential to accommodate different geographical, cultural, and socioeconomic factors. Continuous evaluation and improvement of the model are necessary to address any shortcomings and ensure its long-term sustainability in shaping sustainable and resilient cities for the future.

5.2.2 Best practices

Paris and Barcelona represent two complementary implementation pathways to a 15-minute city. Paris is best characterised as a ***network-and-programme model***: it scales proximity by investing in citywide active-mobility networks (Plan Vélo), formal pedestrian policy (Plan Piéton), and distributed interventions such as school streets, reinforced by democratic legitimacy tools like the 2025 vote on additional pedestrianised “garden roads.”

Barcelona, by contrast, is a ***spatial-operating-unit model***: superblocks reorganise the street hierarchy to make local trips safer and public space more usable, supported by complementary demand management (ZBE) and a strong health/exposure evidence base, including both modelled citywide benefits and observed local pollutant reduction.

Paris (France)

Paris is widely treated as a reference implementation of the “15-minute city” (ville du quart d’heure) because it frames urban performance primarily in terms of *time-to-access* essential daily functions (education, shopping, health, leisure, green space) rather than vehicle speed or road capacity. The concept is closely associated with Carlos Moreno and has been formalised in Paris’ public narrative as a proximity-based development model.

Paris has pursued this through a combined strategy and policy, Paris' Plan Vélo (2021–2026) (City's Plan):

- Reconfiguration of the city's operating system (how streets are allocated, how school function, how local public space is organised)
- Rebalancing street space away from private vehicle
- Increasing the cycling network build-out (Plan Vélo targets a "100% cyclable" city, with 180 km of new protected/secured cycling routes)
- Upgrading school-adjacent streets as a high-leverage intervention point, safe and walkable school trip
- Walkability and pedestrian priority, creating or expanding pedestrian cores in each arrondissement, and extending car-free time/space programmes (City's plan includes commitments such as pedestrianising 100 new streets near educational/public institutions by 2026)
- Neighbourhood-scale changes with visible democratic hooks (Increasing technical programmes with public participation mechanisms that provide legitimacy for reallocating street space)

<https://www.wri.org/insights/paris-15-minute-city>

<https://cdn.paris.fr/paris/2021/12/08/2fc9cb8ad6db58b6bfde3e6ccfc4c48c.pdf>

<https://www.weforum.org/videos/paris-is-planning-to-become-a-15-minute-city-897c12513b/>

Figure 6. Implementation of the Plan Vélo (2021–2026) in Paris

Barcelona (Spain)

Elements of the 15-minute city can be found in Barcelona's Superblocks philosophy, pedestrianized blocks that are accessible to a small number of vehicles.

Barcelona’s “superblocks” (superilles) are widely discussed as a concrete, design-led pathway to 15-minute city outcomes.

The central idea is to reorganise movement:

- keep through traffic primarily on perimeter/arterial streets,
- reduce and calm traffic inside the superblock, and
- repurpose internal streets for walking, cycling, play, greenery, and local social life.

C40’cities documentation describes superblocks as a hierarchical street system that limits through traffic and frees streets for recreation and community use, supported by tactical urbanism and participation.

A series of actions undertaken in the city aim to increase citizens’ access to entertainment, cultural events, and local markets.

The city has transformed its streets with the aim of reclaiming public spaces for citizens from grey infrastructure (road spaces or car parks). Its goal is to acquire 1 million m² of public space in the coming years and dedicate it to sustainable mobility and green streets.

Barcelona’s superblocks have commonly employed adaptable, incremental interventions (often characterised as tactical urbanism) to test layouts, manage uncertainty, and iterate based on observed use and feedback—reducing delivery risk relative to “at once” reconstruction.

The Barcelona green axes plan aims to transform one third of the streets within its 19th century extension grid (Eixample streets), increasing the tree cover and the vegetation, adopting sustainable urban drainage systems, limiting motor traffic, and providing a safer and more comfortable environment for pedestrians, cyclists, and other social activities in healthier environments (27).

A health impact assessment, by Mueller et al (2020), estimated that implementing a full superblock network (hundreds of units) could prevent hundreds of premature deaths annually, with benefits driven primarily by reduced NO₂, noise, heat, and increased green space and physical activity (33).

Barcelona’s superblock strategy sits within broader efforts to reduce car externalities. A key reinforcing policy is the ZBE (Low Emission Zone) within the ring roads, launched 1 January 2020, which restricts the most polluting vehicles during defined hours.

However, there are many governance challenges to deal with the risks or limitations raised from the transformation of the city as traffic and pollution displacement, distributional equity issues, and political contention around access or parking.

Figure 7. Accessibility considerations in the superblocks' network of Barcelona (Ferrer-Ortiz, C.; Marquet, O.; Mojica, L.; Vich, G. Barcelona under the 15-Minute City Lens: Mapping the Accessibility and Proximity Potential Based on Pedestrian Travel Times. *Smart Cities*, 2022, 5, 146–161)

5.3 Transit-Oriented Development (TOD)

5.3.1 The model

Transit-oriented development (TOD) has emerged as an innovative urban planning approach. By reinstating the principles of compact, mixed-use developments, TOD offers a sustainable alternative to the widespread trend of urban sprawl prevalent in many cities today (10).

The Transit Oriented Development (TOD) model is a practice whereby low-density areas located near train stations or other modes and are primarily used for residential purposes, are converted into residential areas with more urban functions and higher density, with these stations at the center of their development. The core philosophy of TOD revolves around creating vibrant, self-sufficient neighbourhoods that promote a harmonious blend of residential, commercial, and recreational spaces, thereby enhancing the quality of urban life and reducing dependence on motorized transportation (45). Concentrating density and mixed uses near stations increases ridership, enabling higher frequency and better cost recovery—often the critical condition for effective mass transit.

TOD has emerged as a popular and influential planning concept in the United States, as a response to the ongoing dispersion of the communities. It is a spatial planning and transport integration model that concentrates higher-density, mixed-use development within walkable catchments of high-capacity public transport nodes and corridors, coupled with pedestrian- and cycling-supportive street design and parking and demand-management measures.

In some large Asian cities, including Hong Kong, Singapore and Tokyo, TOD has been very successful and has delivered compact and very high density urban development focused around rail transit stations.

Although TOD did not focus on creating a neighbourhood but more on reorganizing an area functionally around rapid transit options, elements such as enhanced mobility, pedestrian friendliness, public safety, public space amenities and alternative suburban living and working environments refer to traditional neighbourhood qualities. The system's main priority is to promote walking through a pleasant environment that ensures unimpeded pedestrian movement. The three conditions that must be met are the promotion of equal access to pedestrian mobility for all, the creation of pleasant walkways through lively areas where relevant uses (commerce, recreation, etc.) have developed, and the protection of pedestrians from various elements that may hinder them (e.g., weather phenomena) through the development of appropriate urban equipment. Similar conditions must prevail for cycling. The role of public transport stations is to serve as hubs connecting pedestrian and bicycle networks with the area. For this reason, distances from the hub should be less than 1,000 meters, so that it is easy to access on foot or by bicycle.

In Table 2 the basic dimensions that characterize the TOD model are presented (45).

Table 2: Dimensions constitute the TOD model (based on literature review)

<i>Diversity</i>	A mix of land uses within the area surrounding a transit station, a balanced integration of residential, commercial, employment, recreational and civic spaces
<i>Density</i>	Density is crucial for improving transit performance
<i>Design</i>	Urban design and aesthetic make TOD area attractive and functional
<i>Distance to Transit</i>	Transit system increases the convenience of using public transit
<i>Destination Accessibility</i>	Enhanced accessibility requires efficient transit networks that connect key urban areas
<i>Demand Management</i>	Strategies and policies such as parking management, congestion pricing, and incentives for using public transit or non-motorized transportation are integral to influence travel behaviour towards more sustainable modes

By reconfiguring the land use–transport relationship to prioritise public transport and short active trips, TOD is widely associated with *sustainability* outcomes: it can reduce private vehicle-kilometres travelled, lower transport-related greenhouse gas emissions and local air pollutants, and limit land-consumptive urban expansion by supporting compact growth patterns.

TOD is a set of transportation and land use planning principles and strategies that are sweeping the nation by connecting communities with vibrant, people-centric places in city after city. The main

objective of TOD is to create sustainable, liveable communities centred around efficient public transit systems. By enhancing mobility options and reducing dependence on private vehicles, TOD contributes to more dynamic, resilient, and environmentally responsible urban environments.

At the same time, TOD can strengthen urban *resilience* by diversifying mobility options and reducing systemic dependence on fuel-intensive travel, thereby improving the capacity of households and cities to absorb shocks such as fuel price volatility, network disruptions, and extreme weather events that impair road-based mobility.

However, the extent to which TOD delivers these benefits is contingent on implementation quality, including reliable transit service, safe first/last-mile access, and governance tools that manage displacement and ensure equitable access to transit and essential services. Additionally, TOD has a profound impact on real estate prices and living costs. Careful planning and policy interventions are required to prevent socio-economic disparities and ensure equitable access to affordable housing in transit-rich areas.

5.3.2 Best practices

Hong Kong (China)

Hong Kong’s Mass Transit Railway (MTR) is a typical example of transit-oriented development because station-area intensification is structurally integrated with metro delivery through the MTR “Rail + Property” (R+P) model, in which development rights and land value uplift around rail investments are leveraged to finance network expansion and operations while producing high-density, mixed-use communities directly connected to stations (26).

This TOD features modern stations crowned by towering residential and commercial edifices. The MTR Corporation’s vision extends beyond mere transit; it creates vibrant, vertically integrated neighbourhoods where daily life orbits around the pulse of the railway. This harmonious blend of transit and architecture not only alleviates traffic congestion but also cultivates interconnected urban spaces, demonstrating the power of design in shaping dynamic cities.

The core policy mechanism is therefore not only urban design (compact, walkable station catchments) but also a governance-and-finance architecture that links transport infrastructure to property development and value capture, creating strong incentives to coordinate land use with transit service.

This type of development supports low-car urbanism by concentrating trip origins and destinations in rail-accessible locations and reinforcing public transport as the default mode for daily mobility. The main limitations typically highlighted in the literature relate to distributional outcomes—particularly affordability and displacement risks around premium station locations—and the institutional preconditions required to replicate the model.

Figure 8. The aerial view of Tin Shui Wai in 2016. It is a typical Hong Kong new town, confined by open rural areas and connected to other districts with mass transit railway (MTR) and other public transportation services (26).

Copenhagen, (Denmark)

Copenhagen’s long-running Finger Plan is among the most referenced European TOD strategies, (since 1947) which deliberately concentrated growth along five “fingers” radiating from the city centre, each aligned with commuter rail lines and interspersed with green wedges (24).

The early adoption of a comprehensive and adaptive urban plan has created a well-balanced, award-winning metropolitan area that combines residential neighbourhoods with green areas and access to public transport.

This structured growth facilitated transit-oriented urbanization decades before the TOD concept became globally mainstream. Copenhagen’s deeply embedded cycling culture and early investments in pedestrian infrastructure created a mobility ecosystem where public and non-motorized transport modes dominate.

This corridor-based structure provides many benefits: it creates predictable, transit-served growth areas, supports viable rail service through concentrated demand, and preserves strategically important open space that can contribute to environmental buffering and recreational capacity. In sustainability terms, the model is associated with compact urban form, reduced car dependence relative to low-density expansion, and the protection of green wedges that help contain land take. It supports redundancy and robustness by anchoring regional accessibility to high-capacity rail corridors and safeguarding green infrastructure that can mitigate climate stresses (e.g., heat and stormwater) when paired with local adaptation measures.

Key implementation conditions include long-horizon spatial governance, consistent coordination between transport and land-use authorities, and the management of development pressures in station areas to avoid inequitable accessibility gains.

Figure 9. Illustration of the 1947 Finger Plan of Copenhagen

5.4 Lessons Learned

The model of 15-min city was developed as a response to the structural inefficiencies and inequities of car-dependent urbanization, by **reframing the city around proximity; focus on local, distributed access (polycentric neighbourhoods), improving walk/cycle conditions.**

The model of Transit-Oriented Development (TOD) emerged to address the failure of transit to perform well in low-density, dispersed urban form, by **concentrating demand near high-capacity transit; focus on corridor and node-based access (stations and transit networks).**

Although the different approach development, both two models are designed to address some common challenges:

1. Increase of accessibility: spatial inequalities, travel poverty (high costs and poor service), exclusion of non-drivers (youth, elderly, disabled people, low-income households)
2. Negative feedback loop of car dependence: reduce vehicle-kilometres travelled, reduce land devoted to parking/roads, promote compactness and efficient infrastructure provision
3. Contribution to public health and safety: increasing active mobility, reduction of environmental burdens, increasing social interaction
4. Economic productivity and urban competitiveness: reduce time in congestion, strengthen local economies, stabilize transit finances.
5. Climate mitigation and energy resilience: lower emissions by active mobility and shorter trip lengths, supporting local public spaces.

In the following Table 3, comparison of the two models in specific criteria is presented.

Table 3: The comparison of the two models in specific criteria

Criteria	15-min city model	TOD model
Common policy instruments	Local service planning Complete streets Cycling networks Public space upgrades Local economic supports	Upzoning around stations Parking reform Value capture Joint development Station-area plans
Governance emphasis	Cross-sector coordination of services (schools, health, retail, public realm)	Integration of land-use regulation Transit investment Development finance
Performance metrics	Time-based access to essentials Accessibility indices Walk/cycle comfort and safety	Ridership Mode share Station-area jobs/housing balance Walk access share Parking utilization
Implementation bottlenecks	Service capacity Local opposition Measurement ambiguity Employment geography	Land assembly Financing First/last mile, Transit service quality/capacity
Equity issues & risks	Gentrification due to amenity Displacement risk Uneven feasibility Employment geography	Displacement due to transit Benefits captured by higher-income households Insufficient ““first/last mile” connectivity excessive park-and-ride and parking

6 The Sociotechnical system

6.1 Multiple levels of a socio-technical system as a nested hierarchy

Urban environment is complex, interconnected ecosystem, comprises a multitude of interrelated sociotechnical systems, which provide urban communities with the services required to address societal needs. Urban environment also is increasingly challenged by diverse environmental, social, technological and economic stressors. The rapid pace of globalization and urbanization has heightened the frequency and impact of crises, ranging from climate-induced extreme weather events to global pandemics and supply chain disruptions. The consequences of these stressors are not so simple making the responds of these quite complicated.

The above challenges are not single issues but are systemic, in the sense that they are tied in complex ways to prevailing economic, technological and social systems (15).

Socio-technical system means the interlinked mix of technologies, infrastructures, organizations, markets, regulations, and user practices.

Existing systems are maintained, defended and improved by incumbent actors whose actions are guided by deeply entrenched rules and institutions named “**socio-technical regimes**”.

Transport system is a socio-technical system: (as it also mentioned in Deliverable 2.5)

- It involves human actors and institutions: citizens, operators, planners, regulators, emergency services and other agencies (Actor, Governance Instrument).
- It is shaped by norms, regulations, policies and informal practices: regulations, legal constraints, governance levels, data sharing agreements, roles and responsibilities.
- It is influenced by behavioural responses and social vulnerability: mode choice, route choice, behavioural nudges, incentives, inequities across social groups.

Figure 10 provides the socio-technical system for transport in an urban context. The system is a configuration of elements that include formal and informal institutions, preferences and habits of car drivers, schemes by transport planners, infrastructure, car manufacturers and suppliers and scientific knowledge.

Urban mobility systems are particularly vulnerable to disruptions as they play a crucial role in the functioning of cities. Mobility disruptions, from the small, unnoticeable, expected and endemic problems (accidents, infrastructure breakdowns) to large, acute and unexpected events (black events, pandemics, droughts), dismantle operational hypotheses and challenge the status quo. Such mobility disruptions have cascading effects that can further destabilize social, economic and environmental systems.

The management of mobility disruptions demands holistic approach that addresses complex challenges as a result of complexities and interconnections between the transportation system and other critical infrastructure and social systems.

Figure 10. The socio-technical system for transport system

The multi-level perspective (MLP), as explained by F.Geels (2002), (2007), (2011), (2012), provides the framework of a socio-technical system consisting of three levels (15-18).

niches: the area with protected spaces, for the generation and development of radical innovations, new technologies and practices, **socio-technical regimes:** the dominant system, the area of established practices and associated rules, the stability of existing technological development, infrastructures and regulations, and an exogenous **socio-technical landscape:** consists of slow changing external factors, exogenous trends.

The MLP is a widely used analytical framework for conceptualising and understanding socio-technical transitions, as the result of dynamic interactions among the three levels. The socio-technical

approach addresses stability and change in the systems that perform core functions for society but also provides insights into the barriers and opportunities that societies face in achieving systemic issues.

a) **Niches**, emerging novelties, which are “protected spaces”, where new technologies and practices develop, such as research and development laboratories, subsidized demonstration projects, or small market niches in which users are willing to support emerging innovations. Niche actors such as inventors, start-up companies, firms, work on radical innovations that deviate from existing regimes, and hope that their promising novelties are eventually used in the regime or even replace it. This is no easy task, because the existing regime is stabilized by many lock-in mechanisms. So, innovations may remain stuck in niches for a long period of time.

Niches are often carried out by experimental or demonstration projects, which allow niche actors to learn about innovations in real-life circumstances. Niches gain momentum if expectations become more broadly accepted, learning processes on different dimensions such as technology, market demand, policy issues, user behaviour, result in a stable configuration.

b) **Socio-technical regime**, a well-entrenched socio-technical system, based on alignments of existing technologies, regulations, user patterns and practices, infrastructures, industry structure, policy, techno-scientific knowledge and cultural discourses. The system elements are reproduced, maintained and changed by incumbent actors such as firms, engineers, users, policymakers, special interest groups and civil society actors. Regime actors are connected through “strong social, institutional, organizational, and cognitive relationships” and their behaviour depends upon a shared set of rules which create lock-in mechanisms. Examples of regime rules include mutual perceptions and expectations, shared values and beliefs, preferences on institutional arrangements, policy priorities, cognitive routines, and consumption patterns.

In existing regimes, innovation is mostly incremental because of lock-in mechanisms and path dependence. Examples of lock-in mechanisms are: economic lock-in as investments that create vested interests against change, social lock-in as consumer lifestyles, cognitive routines and political lock-in as regulations and laws that create market entry barriers and policy networks that favour incumbents.

The stability of urban sociotechnical systems and their capability to fulfil societal needs result from the alignment between the rules agreed by regime actors and the exogenous contextual developments embedded in the landscape level. The presence of misalignment requires changing the sociotechnical configuration of both urban systems and the regimes which regulate their functioning. This pressure for change weakens incumbent sociotechnical configurations and generates a window of opportunity for niche actors who are willing to engage in the dynamics of urban innovation.

Figure 11 provides an ideal-typical representation of how the three levels interact dynamically in the unfolding of socio-technical transitions (18).

c) **Socio-technical landscape**, a wider context, which forms an exogenous environment consists of wider external pressures that influence and shape the overall conditions for transitions. These pressures include climate change, demographics, geopolitics, cultural values, economic growth, broad political coalitions, cultural and normative values, environmental problems. While regimes refer to rules that enable and constrain activities within communities, the landscape refers to wider technology-external factors.

Increasing structuration
of activities in local practices

Figure 11. The socio-technical system by F.Geels (18)

The multi-level perspective argues that the system operates in a dynamic condition. The relation between the three concepts can be understood as a nested hierarchy. The functioning of urban sociotechnical systems strongly depends upon the complex interdependencies linking their elements. As mentioned before, system elements including citizens, organizations, culture, policy and regulations, technology, markets, and physical urban infrastructure components, are composing a sociotechnical system which is connected by coevolutionary relationships and their interplay depends upon existing sociotechnical arrangements.

These arrangements make the system dynamically stable but also resistant to change. Therefore, when new technologies are introduced, they “must compete with technologies that benefit from well-developed systems around them” (18) and which have gained precise user understanding.

In this framework, acceleration of sociotechnical transitions involves three mutually reinforcing processes: increasing momentum of niche innovations; weakening of existing systems; and strengthening exogenous pressures, which when aligned can create windows of opportunity. The resulting sociotechnical transitions go beyond the adoption of new technologies and include investment in new infrastructures, establishment of new markets, development of new social preferences, and adjustment of user practices. Sociotechnical transitions gain momentum when multiple innovations are linked together, improving the functionality of each and acting in combination to reconfigure systems.

6.2 Disruptions in regime level

Any change at the landscape level creates pressure on the existing regime. The changes are slow trends (climate change, demographic shifts) or sudden events or shocks (pandemics, wars, financial crises). Concerning the shocks, they are characterized by being exogenous to a specific regime, time-limited (they happen in a specific period) and high intensity (disturbing entrenched).

Landscape pressures and shocks can trigger the existing regime destabilization. The disruptions can be in material structures (transport infrastructure failures, assets are destroyed), in economic structures (sudden price changes, bankruptcies), in cultural or cognitive structures (taken-for-granted assumptions are questioned).

However, they do not automatically produce radical transitions. Sometimes this can lead to radical departures from existing trajectories, while at other times existing systems can be more resilient, adapting, or reconfiguring in response to a shock (17). It depends on how actors interpret the shock and which niches are ready to scale.

Destabilization of the regime creates windows of opportunity for niche innovations. Niche innovations build up internal momentum, through learning processes, price/performance

improvements and support from groups. New innovations in mainstream markets compete with the existing regime.

Depending on context, a shock can lead to different transition pathways (based on Geels & Schot's pathway typology (2007) (16)):

- **Reproduction:** regime absorbs the shock, makes only minimal changes and returns to the old trajectory
- **Incremental reorientation:** regime adapts with limited reforms e.g. efficiency improvements, risk management but the core structure remains.
- **Reconfiguration:** regime integrates niche elements (new technologies, practices) to solve problems, potentially changing its structure over time.
- **De-alignment and re-alignment:** shock erodes regime coherence; several niche trajectories coexist for a period before a new regime forms around one of them.

Successful transitions typically happen when niche innovations gain momentum, align with wider social changes, and receive institutional acceptance. However, incumbent actors, political interests, and infrastructural lock-ins often create barriers for transition.

6.3 Anticipated Stressors and Uncertainties in the Landscape

Landscape exhibits differentiated dynamics, some factors change only on very long timescales (slow trend), others change over the course of decades, and others through sudden events or shocks. All these put pressure on existing regime.

In the context of transport land use systems and mobility, there is a range of stressors. From Deliverable 2.1, there is the following categorization of the events:

Daily Stressors: traffic congestion, parking shortages, minor signal malfunctions. These events are frequent and short-lived but cumulatively erode mobility efficiency.

Mid-Scale Events: localised flooding, public protests affecting key transport corridors, strikes disrupting bus and metro services, moderate snowstorms. They require tactical responses such as rerouting and service headway adjustments.

Large-Scale Disruptions: major natural disasters (e.g., floods covering entire districts, earthquakes), widespread power outages and conflicts that damage transport infrastructure. They necessitate strategic interventions and long-term recovery.

Generally, the anticipated stressors, pressures and deep uncertainties for the future that influence land-use and transport systems are the following (4):

- **Urbanisation and its impact on infrastructure resilience.** Rapid urbanization exerts immense pressure on all the urban system networks such as transportation. The infrastructure system has to sustain the demands of growth, the consequential pressures and loads maintaining its functionality and resilience to future failures and shocks.
- **Climate change and environmental pressures.** Climate change constitutes one of the most significant stressors for transport and land use systems. Extreme temperatures, flooding, sea-level rise, and windstorms threaten infrastructure durability and operational continuity. Critical transport infrastructure assets—bridges, tunnels, railways, ports, and urban intersections—are increasingly exposed to climate risks. Land use patterns also influence vulnerability; for instance, development in flood-prone or heat-intensive areas increases systemic exposure. Future systems must therefore be designed to withstand increased climatic variability, incorporate nature-based solutions for flood mitigation and heat reduction, ensure redundancy in mobility networks, maintain accessibility during extreme events.
- **Decarbonisation policies and possible fossil-fuel price volatility** may rapidly shift mode choices and fleet composition (EVs, shared mobility, micro-mobility), with uneven spatial impacts depending on charging infrastructure and grid capacity.
- **Socio-demographic change and behavioural uncertainty.** Ageing populations, changing household structures, migration and evolving work patterns (e.g. hybrid and remote work) modify daily activity patterns and space–time geographies of mobility. Behavioural uncertainty is equally important: post-pandemic shifts toward remote work, e-commerce, and flexible travel patterns have begun reshaping land-use functions and trip generation in ways that challenge traditional forecasting models
- **Technological disruption and automation.** Connected and automated vehicles (CAVs), on-demand mobility platforms and data-driven traffic management create new accessibility patterns and may either reinforce sprawl or support compact, multimodal cities, depending on regulation and pricing. Their reliability under extreme weather or cyber-attacks remains uncertain, posing new systemic risks.
- **Technological and financial constraints.** The aging infrastructure system and the absence of the integration of smart and digital solutions are barriers for the infrastructure being resilient to adapt to pressures.
- **Institutional and governance uncertainties.** Fragmented responsibilities for land use, transport, environmental protection and emergency management hinder coherent responses and can delay adaptation investments. Improving governance structures and fostering multi-stakeholder collaboration play a critical role.

7 Resilience – Antifragility in transportation systems

7.1 Resilience in transportation systems

Urban transportation systems are exposed to different types of disturbances or unexpected disruptive events or disasters. A disturbance refers to any mechanism by which mobility is reduced or the cost to maintain desired levels of mobility drastically increases. In case of the concept of disaster, Rodrigue J. (2024) mentions that it is an event which creates extensive damage to people and infrastructure and it is going beyond the anticipated capabilities to respond (37). The lack of risk assessment and appropriate preparedness are critical parameters for the consequences.

As it is mentioned in Deliverable 2.1, there are different event categories:

- natural disasters, environmental hazards (hurricanes, floods, fires),
- human-made events (strikes, cultural events, terrorist attacks)
- system failures (by human error or mismanagement).

Although there is no common definition of resilience, the concept is broadly examined as a property related to a system's recovery from disruptions and is characterized as a descriptive concept that portrays emergent functions and properties (43). Resilience is commonly used to describe the ability of an entity or system to bounce back to a normal condition after its original state being affected by a disruptive event or to withstand an external disturbance and proactively recover towards a new stable state (29).

Building resilience capacity through landscape and urban planning requires that planners and designers identify the stochastic processes and disturbances that a particular landscape or city is likely to face, the frequency and intensity of these events, and how cities can build the adaptive capacity to respond to these disturbances while remaining in a functional state (2), (40). JAhern in his research, highlights the need for resilience effective management in order to move from the “fail-safe” direction to resilience, the capacity of systems to reorganize and recover from change and disturbance without changing to other states, in other words, systems that are “safe to fail.” (2).

Among other researchers, Ahern J. proposes five urban planning and design strategies for building urban resilience including:

- **multifunctionality**: efficient spatially, combining functions, increasingly compact cities
- **redundancy and modularization**: are achieved when multiple elements or components provide

the similar or backup functions

- **diversity**, a high level of economic and social diversity have a more complex response to adapt change and socio-economic disturbance
- **multi-scale networks and connectivity**: complex networks build resilience capacity through circuitry that maintains functional connectivity after network disturbance.
- **adaptive planning and design**: conceives the “problem” of making decisions with imperfect knowledge about change and uncertain disturbances as an “opportunity” to “learn-by-doing”.

The concept of resilience is a topic of interest in transportation systems. There are various types of research on reliance in transportation systems providing different definitions of the concept from different perspectives. Transport network resilience is defined as the ability of a transport network to absorb shocks, maintain functionality, adapt to and resist the negative effects of disruptive events, and rapidly recover to a state of equilibrium (42), (43).

It emphasizes the importance of anticipating and reducing one’s vulnerability in combination with the monitoring efforts, the ability to respond to and the capacity to learn from crises.

In Figure 12, the different characteristics of resilience are presented in a graphical representation of a system performance in face of a disruptive event. The definition of the concepts are:

1. **Robustness**: The network’s ability to maintain functions during a disruption.
2. **Vulnerability**: The risk of disruption and loss of functionality, representing a network’s susceptibility to perturbations and adverse consequences that lead to performance loss.
3. **Redundancy**: The ability of a network to offer alternative options or provide additional capacity to replace capacity loss during a disruption.
4. **Resourcefulness**: The availability of supplies and resources and the ability to mobilise them to restore functionality during a perturbation.
5. **Rapidity**: The speed at which functionality of a transport network is restored.
6. **Reliability**: The probability that a transport network will function successfully for an intended period of time under operating conditions.
7. **Mitigation strategies**: Retrofitting or enhancing transport infrastructure, with a focus on vulnerable components or nodes of a network, to improve the ability to absorb the adverse effects of disruption events.

In the “Urban Mobility Resilience Roadmap” of the European Road Transport Research Advisory Council (ERTRAC) (2021), which has an intention to provide guidance on research and innovation priorities to address the issues on the resilience of the urban mobility system, seven key principles are mentioned for building resilient urban mobility systems.

These principles are: *reflectiveness, robustness, redundancy, flexibility, resourcefulness, inclusiveness, integration.*

Figure 12. Schematic of performance of a resilient system by Ch.Wan et al (2018) (46)

7.2 Antifragility in transportation systems

The concept of antifragile transport system goes beyond being just robust or resilient. It is a network that improves and adapts to stressors, shocks and disruptions to become stronger and more efficient, using techniques like AI-driven traffic control, diverse transport modes to learn from failures and enhance overall performance. While resilience aims for recovery to a pre-existing state, antifragility seeks systems that benefit from disruption, potentially opening new routes or learning new flow patterns that improve overall system capacity (e.g., discovering a new efficient detour permanently).

The analysis in Deliverable D2.1, identified specific mechanisms through which urban mobility systems strengthen post-disruption:

- Redundancy Activation: Dormant capacity becomes active, creating more robust networks.

- Innovation Acceleration: Disruptions catalyse rapid adoption of new mobility technologies and services.
- Behavioural Learning: Users develop more sophisticated multi-modal capabilities.
- Institutional Evolution: Governance structures adapt to manage increased complexity
- Cross-System Integration: Previously isolated systems become interconnected.

From the antifragile lens, policy, infrastructure and governance can be designed so that such disturbances may trigger desirable land-use and mobility transitions e.g. permanent reallocations of road space to active modes after successful temporary trials. An antifragile transport–land use system improves through volatility, leverages crises for transformation, enables innovation on the occasion of disruptions, incorporates feedback loops that strengthen system performance. Examples include cities that expanded cycling infrastructure during crises, using disruption as a catalyst for long-term mobility reform. Among these examples is Paris, which during the COVID-19 pandemic rapidly deployed over 50 km of pop-up cycle lanes ("coronapistes")—many later made permanent—leveraging the crisis for ambitious cycling expansion; London, which introduced emergency cycleways resulting in a 40% rise in cycling post-lockdown; and Brussels, which accelerated its "Superquick Cycling Network" amid disruptions to promote resilient mobility.

Traditional planning and operations frameworks largely strive for robustness (resisting change) or resilience (bouncing back). AntifragiCity adopts a different stance: urban mobility systems should benefit from variability and disruption, by learning, adapting and reconfiguring in ways that improve performance, equity and sustainability over time.

From the project perspective and as synthesized in Deliverable D2.5 "Ontology of Urban Events Development", an antifragile urban mobility system should be able to:

- Maximise individual and collective mobility under uncertainty
- Adapt network configuration and land-use to improve accessibility and reduce vulnerability
- Foster active and low-emission modes while maintaining service quality
- Respond intelligently to disruptions through rapid sensing, scenario evaluation, adaptive response actions, and learning from repeated events
- Maintain equity and inclusiveness, ensuring that vulnerable groups are not adversely affected and that benefits are fairly distributed
- Coordinate multiple actors and governance levels, including emergency services, agencies and citizens
- Integrate heterogeneous data (traffic sensors, governance datasets, equity indicators, environmental data, digital-twin outputs, and safety/incident records) into a consistent knowledge graph and query layer

7.3 Are the models of 15-min city and TOD be resilient and antifragile?

The “15-minute city” and Transit-Oriented Development (TOD) can be framed as urban development paradigms with strong potential to enhance resilience and, under specific design and governance conditions, to exhibit antifragile properties. In this report, resilience is understood as the capacity of an urban system to absorb disturbances—such as energy price shocks, extreme-weather events, public-health disruptions, and infrastructure failures—while maintaining essential functions. Antifragility goes beyond robustness or recovery: it describes systems that improve because of stressors, using disruption as a trigger for learning, reconfiguration, and performance gains (38, 41).

From a resilience perspective, the 15-minute city strengthens urban functioning by reducing systemic dependence on long-distance travel and single mobility modes. By concentrating everyday services—healthcare, education, food access, public services, and recreation—within short travel times, it mitigates exposure to network-wide disruptions (e.g., fuel constraints, congestion collapse) and enables continued access to essentials through mode substitution (walking, cycling, micromobility, local transit). Similarly, well-executed TOD enhances resilience by coupling compact, mixed-use station areas with high-capacity public transport, thereby lowering vulnerability to private-vehicle constraints and maintaining accessibility even under conditions of economic or energy volatility. In both models, resilience increases when the urban form supports distributed access (multiple local centers and station areas) rather than concentrating critical functions into a small number of dominant hubs.

The antifragile potential of these models emerges when their spatial, economic, and operational structures promote adaptive capacity through modularity, diversity, and feedback. The 15-minute city becomes antifragile when it supports fine-grained mixed use, small blocks, and adaptable building typologies (especially flexible ground floors), enabling rapid shifts in service provision and land-use intensity as demand changes. Frequent, low-cost interventions—such as pilot street redesigns, tactical traffic calming, and iterative public-realm upgrades—create “small experiments” that allow learning and optimization after shocks, producing measurable improvements rather than mere recovery. TOD can exhibit antifragility when implemented as network TOD (polycentric station systems with robust interconnections), supported by redundant access channels (walk-bike-feeder transit-micromobility), and operational flexibility in transit service planning (e.g., scalable frequency, rerouting, and contingency operations). Under disruption, demand can redistribute across nodes, revealing weak links and guiding targeted reinforcement of both service patterns and last-mile connectivity.

However, both models may become fragile if implemented as overly optimized, monocultural, or inequitable systems. A 15-minute city strategy can fail to deliver resilience if it remains nominal—

without real service availability, safe active-mobility infrastructure, or affordable access—thereby sustaining hidden car dependence. TOD can become brittle when station areas rely on single megaprojects, narrow economic functions, or a single transit corridor that acts as a “single point of failure.” In both cases, equity is not merely normative but functional: displacement and loss of affordability near services and stations can erode workforce proximity, reduce ridership stability, and weaken the social foundations required for system continuity during shocks.

Accordingly, the degree to which 15-minute city and TOD are resilient or antifragile can be assessed through four interrelated dimensions: (1) redundancy in mobility and access (multiple modes and routes to essentials); (2) diversity of land uses, housing tenures, and economic activities (avoiding monocultures); (3) modularity and capacity for “small failure” (incremental development, adaptable typologies, distributed nodes); and (4) adaptive governance and feedback loops (monitoring, piloting, and iterative recalibration). When these conditions are met, both paradigms can be positioned not only as strategies for sustainability and accessibility, but as frameworks for urban systems that maintain function under stress—and, in the antifragile case, become structurally and operationally stronger through disturbance-driven learning.

8 Development of a Conceptual Model

The nexus between transportation, land use and travel patterns is supported by the transport-land use feedback cycle. The framework explains how changes in transport supply (infrastructure, service, cost and time) reshape accessibility. The change of accessibility influences land use patterns, which are translated into travel behaviour as they take place over the existing transport system. And this provides a useful baseline for analysing how shocks propagate through cities.

Cities are confronted with a convergence of acute shocks/disruptions (accidents, infrastructure failures, floods), chronic stresses (congestion, pollution, demographic changes) and systemic crises (pandemics, economic downturns). Different disruptive conditions influence the mobility system in various ways, leading to new equilibrium states and performance statuses.

Urban mobility is a dynamic socio-technical system that results from changing relationships and interactions between individuals, organizations, technology, and the built environment. Feedback loops, non-linearity, and adaptive behaviour define the urban mobility dynamic: it changes over time (e.g., as a result of technology adoption, demographic shifts), responds to shocks or disruptions (e.g., pandemics, climate events), and adapts through feedback (e.g., new congestion policies lead to behaviour change and new congestion patterns).

The disruptions affect the transport land-use cycle through at least four linked directions:

1. network performance and reliability (link failures, service interruptions, capacity drops)
2. generalized travel costs (monetary cost, increased time, discomfort)
3. perceived accessibility (whether people can reliably reach jobs, homes, services)
4. risk feeling (social network)

The transport system's resilience refers to the system's capacity to deal with, adapt to and recover from disruptions, and stress the possibility of moving towards new equilibrium. Mobility serves as the primary adaptive mechanism through which urban systems respond to and learn from disruptions. This view of resilience emphasizes the possibility of regime shifts in the face of shocks or stresses, while its expression in the complex transport sector means that the "same" risk can produce very different outcomes depending on whether the system has redundancy, and adaptive capacity or whether the system is optimized so tightly for efficiency that small failures have a knock-on effect.

As presented in 7.1, the resilience of transport systems is determined by the "4 Rs": the **robustness** of the system, the extent to which a deterioration of a system's functions is due to the disruption

(absorptive capacity), the **redundancy**, the provision of additional and alternative capacity, the **resourcefulness**, the availability of supplies and resources and the ability to mobilise them to restore functionality during a perturbation, the **rapidity of recovery**, the time needed for a transport system to get back to the service level or level of operations before the disruption took place (time of recovery). This lens is particularly useful for transport because it bridges engineering concerns (assets, networks) with institutional concerns (governance, operations, emergency management).

The Figure 13 represents the **holistic conceptual framework model** to address urban mobility dynamics, integrating transport–land use interactions, resilience-oriented planning, human-centric design principles under conditions of uncertainty and external stressors. These interactions are not static, but they evolve over time and across spatial scales.

At the core of the model lies the integration of transport and land use dynamics, as a primary driver of accessibility and spatial form. Urban form, land-use mix, and transport infrastructure determine accessibility patterns.

A disruption reveals whether a transport land-use system is fragile.

Exogenous disruptions are represented as hazard processes (e.g., floods, heatwaves, energy or cyber shocks). External characteristics of a disruptive event shape how strongly it affects a transport system and how it responds and recovers. In Table 4, different external, exogenous disruption drivers and their definitions are presented. The possible indicator of each driver is connected to the type of disruption. For example, the driver of spatial extent could be evaluated as [km² affected] in case of a flood, or [%of network links] in case of an accident.

Table 4: Exogenous Disruption Drivers and their definitions

a/a	Exogenous Disruption Drivers	Definition
1	Hazard Intensity	<i>The magnitude or severity of the disruptive agent (physical force, load, or impact level)</i>
2	Duration	<i>How long the disruptive conditions persist, including the time over which the system is exposed</i>
3	Spatial Extent	<i>The geographic footprint of the disruption and the share of the network/region affected</i>
4	Frequency/Recurrence	<i>How often similar disruptions occur and whether they repeat in short cycles</i>
5	Predictability	<i>The degree to which the disruption can be anticipated in advance (lead time and forecast accuracy)</i>
6	Cross-Sector Dependency	<i>The disruption's reliance on, or cascading effects through, non-transport systems that transport depends on (and vice versa)</i>
7	Distributional Asymmetry	<i>Whether impacts are evenly distributed or disproportionately affect certain groups, locations, or trip purposes</i>

These hazards translate into transport impacts through the local risk context, primarily **Exposure** (assets, people, and activities located in affected areas), **Vulnerability** (physical, operational, and social sensitivity), optionally weighted by **Sensitivity** (system dependency on key links/hubs) [Risk=Hazard X Exposure X Vulnerability] [1].

The interaction produces damage in the infrastructure condition (level of service availability, effective capacity) (TI) and network structure (redundancy index, network modularity) (TN). Transport network system vulnerability is the susceptibility of the network to incidents that cause considerable reductions in serviceability (infrastructure capacity, service, cost, time) [2].

The service degradation then reduces network performance and essential accessibility (A). The “essential” accessibility under changing conditions is crucial point that defines the minimum operating level (maintain access to jobs, home, food, safety, healthcare). Accessibility is widely used as an evaluation concept for integrated land-use and transport policy because it connects transport performance to spatial opportunities and social outcomes [3].

The impacts on accessibility trigger responses to maintain the threshold of essential accessibility. The resilient system mobilises a set of its own organizational and operational capabilities under an exogenous disruption. Resilience is decomposed into actionable capabilities: absorptive capacity (the ability to withstand and absorb impacts of disruptions), operational response (response time and after-shock performance level), rapidity of recovery (time to recovery), service prioritization (prioritization of vulnerable users, emergency access) and communication continuity (maintain clear information flows during the event).

Typical immediate resilient responses are: priority to critical corridors (emergency lanes, bus lane, bus priority), controlled level of service, real time re-routing, dynamic operations by adaptive signal control, alternative modes (R) [4].

The following examples disruptions propagate through urban mobility via characteristic casual chains.

- **Transport-related:** congestion → increased travel time → modal shift (e.g., car to bus) → public-transport overload.
- **Environment & weather:** flooding → road/rail closure → rerouting → accessibility drop for emergency services.
- **Utilities & Connectivity:** power outage → signal failure → public-transport headway irregularity → cascading delays.
- **Public space:** protest → street closure → bus re-routing → longer dwell times.

The resilience-oriented re-organization of the transport network system requires urban planning and design strategies that enable the recovery from any disruptive condition. Therefore, the enhancement of the urban transport system's resilience needs to focus on the capabilities of multifunctionality, redundancy and modularization, diversity, multi-scale networks and connectivity, adaptive planning and design [5].

New accessibility challenges affect land-use planning (L) [6] and in turn, these new land use planning & strategies create new transport challenges [7].

The system's property of resilience is expressed through the capacity to respond, monitor, learn, and anticipate. The proposed framework extends beyond the broadly applied conceptualizations of resilience towards the approach of antifragility, enabling systems to learn and improve through disruption.

Translating the conceptual approach of antifragility into transport-land-use planning means designing governance, standards, and investment rules so that disruptions systematically generate improvements rather than repeated reconstruction of the same vulnerabilities. By using different intervention levers such as monitoring capacity, learning rate, institutional flexibility, adaptation investment share, policy of adaptations standards, decision transparency, knowledge retention and transfer, diversity and redundancy, modify and reshape network decisions and planning strategies over time [8].

Antifragile systems not only repair their damages but reconfigure their structure and/or processes after shocks. This aligns with policy guidance emphasizing that climate adaptation in transport requires strategies that manage uncertainty and incorporate iterative risk assessment rather than one-time design fixes. Policy measures reshape land use [9]. New investments and standards restructure transport network [10].

The following primary causal sequences emerged showing how disruptions lead to system enhancement:

- **Disruption → Mobility → Resilience:** Direct pathway where mobility adaptations create more robust post-disruption system configurations.
- **Complexity → Mobility → Adaptation:** System complexity enables diverse mobility responses that through the system's redundancy and resourcefulness lead to adaptation.
- **Technology → Mobility → Emergence:** Integration of new technologies facilitates emergent mobility solutions.
- **Mobility → Network → Governance:** Mobility changes drive network reconfigurations requiring governance evolution.

The analysis identified distinct but interconnected responses across multiple system scales:

- Individual Level: Behavioural adaptations, route choice modifications, modal shifts.
- Network Level: Traffic flow reorganisation, service reconfiguration, emergent routing patterns.
- City Level: Infrastructure adaptation, policy responses, resource reallocation.
- System Level: Comprehensive transformations, new mobility paradigms, technological integration.

This multi-scale framework demonstrates how antifragility and resilience manifest differently across system levels while maintaining the coherent system as-a-whole wide adaptation.

In this framework the *“Behaviour and Social Dynamics”* represents the human-system that shapes how disruptions propagate from the physical transport network into real accessibility outcomes. Behaviour parameter is not treated as a purely external factor; it mediates and modulates multiple causal pathways by influencing (i) travel demand and network loading during disruptions, (ii) social vulnerability and distributional impacts, and (iii) the effectiveness of response and recovery measures in the serviceability of the transport system.

“Governance and Decision-Making Capacity” is the institutional level that determines how effectively the system can anticipate, coordinate, and implement actions across the disruption cycle. While the hazard–exposure–sensitive-vulnerability mechanism explains why disruptions cause damage, the *“Governance & Decision-making Capacity”* explains how well the transport–land-use system absorbs the shock, restores essential function, and potentially improves after the event. The Governance shapes operational preparedness and anticipatory capacity through risk-informed planning, standards and asset management. This includes the ability to integrate climate risk scenarios into design, operation and maintenance. Moreover, Governance is a determinant of response coordination and speed during disruption.

“Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)” do not act as a driver of physical failure in the same way as hazards or exposure; instead, they provide the multi-criteria objective function against which resilience and antifragility are assessed and prioritised. In other words, SDGs ensure that “resilience” is not only to restore traffic flow, but is measured in terms of **safety, equity, environmental performance, public health, and economic continuity**.

Figure 13. Holistic conceptual framework model to address urban mobility dynamics, integrating transport-land use interactions, resilience-oriented planning, human-centric design principles under conditions of uncertainty and external stressors.

Table 5: Indicative KPIs implemented in the framework model

a/a	KPI	Definition
A.1	Transport network system	
	Infrastructure condition	
1	Mobility throughput	<i>Mobility throughput: average multi-modal trips per capita per hour</i>
2	Commuter Flow Centrality	<i>The total number of commuters through a node per hour.</i>
3	Travel time and delays	<i>The total duration a vehicle spends on a journey, encompassing driving, idling, and waiting from origin to destination.</i>
4	Delays in the transport system	<i>The amount of time lost due to transportation delays.</i>
5	Average trip duration per vehicle	<i>The average time a vehicle spends on a trip.</i>
6	Congestion and delays	<i>Calculates the impact of congestion and delays in the urban mobility system, which can be measured by time lost in congestion or the extent of congestion in time or space.</i>
	Network structure	
1	Public transport route network	<i>Further measured by multimodal compatibility, the system of ticket sale and distribution, distance to a bus stop, etc.</i>
2	Public transport efficiency	<i>The occupancy rate of buses, reflecting how effectively public transport vehicles are utilized. It quantifies the proportion of available capacity being used by passengers.</i>
3	Urban roads length per area	<i>The total physical length of roads within a defined urban expanse, typically expressed in kilometres per square kilometer (Km/km²).</i>
A2	Accessibility	
1	Accessibility by car-driving	<i>This indicator can be measured by assessing the percentage of the population with access to a car or the travel time required to reach specific locations by car.</i>
2	Accessibility for emergence rescue	<i>It measures the timeliness of disaster relief efforts and the ability to access necessary emergency infrastructure within a given spatial distribution.</i>
3	Destination Accessibility	<i>Total number of direct destinations accessible.</i>
A3	Land use planning & Strategies	
1	Urban density	<i>The concentration of population in urban areas, which is a key indicator for assessing land resource utilization and urban planning aspects.</i>

2	Density of public services within all area services	<i>The concentration and availability of public services throughout a given geographical area. This indicator assesses how well essential services are distributed and accessible to the population within urban environments.</i>
3	Greening coverage of built-up areas	<i>Proportion of green space within built-up area.</i>
4	Spatial openness	<i>The number of entrances of visibility along the street. This indicator, measured in entrances per meter, quantifies the extent of open sightlines within a given urban space.</i>
5	Land use compactness	<i>The percentages of built-up areas within urban growth boundaries. This indicator assesses how efficiently urban land is utilized, reflecting the concentration of development within a defined urban footprint.</i>

9 Conclusions

This Deliverable D3.1 "Analysis of the Transport network and Land use dynamics" is the key output of Task T3.1 within Work Package 3 (WP3) of the AntifragiCity project, demonstrates the connection between land use and transport networks as a fundamental concept for designing safe, efficient, sustainable, and resilient transport systems and determines interdependent factors influencing transport-land use system dynamics.

Land use and transport infrastructure, closely interlinked, underpinned theoretically in the so-called transport land-use feedback cycle, has been modelled since more than six decades. The nexus between transportation, land use and travel patterns generates various transport problem in cities as for example the traffic congestion where traffic flow reaching network capacity. Urban researchers have sought to formalize this relationship using mathematical, statistical, and logical methods, and to produce models capable of predicting changes to transportation and land use systems as the result of policy measures.

Cities are confronted with a convergence of acute shocks/disruptions (accidents, infrastructure failures, floods), chronic stresses (congestion, pollution, demographic changes) and systemic crises (pandemics, economic downturns). Different disruptive conditions influence the mobility system in various ways, leading to new equilibrium states and performance statuses.

The proposed holistic conceptual framework model addresses urban mobility dynamics, integrating transport–land use interactions, resilience-oriented planning, human-centric design principles under conditions of uncertainty and external stressors. These interactions are not static, but they evolve over time and across spatial scales.

The framework conceptualizes urban mobility as a coupled transport–land use system operating under uncertainty and external stressors. Disruption drivers are translated into system-level risk, shaping how stress propagates into the transport network system, defined by infrastructure condition and network structure/topology. These characteristics determine the magnitude and spatial distribution of accessibility impacts treated as the integrative outcome linking network performance to societal opportunity. Accessibility outcomes interact dynamically with land-use planning and strategies, forming a feedback loop where in land-use decisions reconfigure demand and network loading, while accessibility changes influence activity patterns and location choices. The model further distinguishes resilience as the set of absorptive, response, and recovery capacities that mitigate accessibility losses, and extends this logic to antifragility emphasizing learning-oriented governance, monitoring, and adaptive investment that can improve system performance following stress. Behavioural and social dynamics moderate these relationships by shaping adaptive responses (e.g., mode shift, compliance, risk perception), while governance capacity and sustainability goals act as boundary conditions that define feasibility, priorities, and evaluation criteria (e.g., equity, safety, reliability).

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